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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Countries
CoP	Community of Practice
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GCI	Class Ceiling Index
GE	Gender Equality
GEI	Gender Equality Index
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HE	Higher Education
HEA	Higher Education Authority (Ireland)
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
ISAS	Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic
MLW	Mutual Learning Workshop
MS	EU Member States
NIP	National Impact Plan
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
SII	Summary Innovation Index
UEFISCDI	Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation, Romania
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Gender equality has been one of ERA's priorities for more than a decade. In 2021, most Member States and Associated Countries renewed and reinforced their commitment to gender equality by endorsing the **Ljubljana Declaration**. With the Ljubljana Declaration, the main stakeholder in R&I (EC, MS/AC) agreed on the directions of further development: to address gender-based violence, to move from a gender oriented to an intersectional approach to gender equality and to focus on GEPs as the most significant instrument to achieve sustainable progress towards gender equality in R&I. The Ljubljana Declaration is a main reference in the **ERA Policy Agenda** – specifically in **ERA Action 5** focusing on gender equality and inclusiveness. In total 22 Member States and three other countries committed in a written statement to ERA Action 5: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Georgia (observer), Ireland, Israel (AC), Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, the Netherlands, Norway (AC), Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.

Compared to the previous ERA period (2015-2020), there is now a more detailed description provided by the European Commission of what is expected from Member States that have committed to pursuing gender equality and inclusiveness. As there is no requirement to formulate a national action plan as in the previous ERA period, there is only limited information available regarding MS/AC priorities, objectives and planned or implemented measures.

To gather comprehensive data on strategies, objectives and measures related to gender equality in the ERA, a survey was conducted among members of the ERA Forum Subgroup Gender and Inclusiveness. Nineteen countries participated in the survey (17 Member States and 2 Associated Countries). With 12 responses the survey reflects the situation of the 'old' Member States (former EU 15) quite well, but not that of the countries that have joined the EU since 2004 (5 responses).

The second WP5 report, based on a survey¹, describes which ERA Action 5 targets have been adopted at national level, which measures are being implemented and whether and what information is being collected on the implementation of measures. It demonstrates that not all objectives are supported by measures and, conversely, that in most countries there is a **lack of information on the implementation of measures** in those areas addressed by the objectives.

Of the countries that have committed to ERA Action 5, just over half have formulated an ERA action plan or a gender equality strategy that refers to ERA. However, even in the absence of a strategic document, the majority of countries represented in the survey have formulated gender equality policy objectives based on ERA action 5. These objectives, however, lack specific, measurable and time-bound objectives (SMART objectives), instead representing a **commitment to address specific challenges without the formulation of concrete targets**. Even though a large number of objectives have been formulated and the topics from ERA Action 5 have been adopted in principle, this is not mirrored in the measures that are planned or implemented in each of these areas. Fourteen countries provide information on at least one measure. Several countries support structural change in HEIs and RPOs or sex/gender-analysis or intersectional research. Only a few countries are implementing

¹ A survey has been distributed among members of the ERA Forum subgroup on gender and inclusiveness in spring 2024. In total 19 countries participated in the survey, 17 Member States and 2 Associated Countries.

measures to promote inclusive career paths, to combat gender-based violence, to promote gender balance in decision-making or to address inequalities beyond gender.

GENDERACTIONplus argues that monitoring has significant potential for steering gender equality policy implementation at the European and national levels. However, this potential is currently untapped, due to a **lack of comparable information** at national level. Given the current data set, it is not feasible to draw comparisons between the status of gender equality policies across Member states and Associated countries, nor to ascertain whether these policies have evolved in a particular direction. Furthermore, an analysis of the consistency and coherence of gender equality policy strategies is not feasible.

The absence of a unified and coherent gender equality policy in the ERA also results in **inefficiencies in the policymaking process**. It is evident that several countries are developing measures in parallel, which results in a lack of coordination and inefficiencies in policy-making. This also allows stakeholders to understand concepts differently which contradicts the assumption of policy-makers at European and national level that there is a coherent and consistent understanding of the concepts used in European documents. Furthermore, the lack of exchange when (re)designing measures also means that existing synergies may not be used and mistakes that have already been made are repeated in other contexts.

The combination of a political steering mechanism in ERA, which relies on voluntary action in the area of gender equality, with a lack of reporting or monitoring on the implementation of gender equality policy at the national level, means that the self-commitment is not perceived as binding.

To further develop – or at least maintain – the status quo of gender equality engagement in ERA, it is essential to complement the voluntary character of political commitment with robust monitoring and an intensified gender equality policy discourse. To achieve this, the following is proposed:

- In order to fully leverage the potential of monitoring for steering policy, it is important in the future to not only request that countries make a commitment to an ERA action on a voluntary basis, but also to ensure that this is translated into a concrete national action plan (binding self-commitment).
- To intensify the European discourse on gender equality by involving high-level policy-makers (e.g. ERAC members).
- To provide a platform for mutual learning and exchange already in the phase of policy development. This would support countries with little experience in particular and provide a possibility to reflect on already implemented measures for more experienced countries.
- To systematically collect information on the implementation of national and/or regional gender equality policies from the start of the implementation period and integrate this information in existing monitoring systems such as the ERA Monitoring Mechanism (ERA Scoreboard, ERA Dashboard) and She Figures.
- To use the results of the monitoring for awareness raising activities (e.g. public presentation of the monitoring at European and national level) and for showcasing identified good practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Building on the Horizon 2020 project GENDERACTION, the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new European Research Area (ERA) through the development of two communities of practice (CoPs), one consisting of representatives of national authorities and the second consisting of representatives of Research Funding Organisations. The network is made up of a total of 22 EU Member States (MS) and 3 Associated Countries (AC), as well as 26 project partners and 14 Associated partners.

Adding the plus sign to the title of the previous GENDERACTION project not only indicates that it is a follow-up project but also makes it explicit that this project also addresses diversity and intersectionality (the gender+ approach).

Specifically, the GENDERACTIONplus project aims to:

- Develop strategic policy advice on existing and emerging policy solutions;
- Enhance the policy-making process by engaging with stakeholders, civil society organisations, and citizens;
- Build capacities, competence, and expertise for gender equality and mainstreaming in Research & Innovation among the policy and RFO community members, with special attention to countries with less comprehensive policies;
- Create impact through communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Thematically, the project focuses on:

- Intersectionality and inclusiveness
- Gender-based violence (GBV)
- The gender dimension in research and innovation
- Monitoring and evaluating gender equality actions in the European Research Area (ERA)
- Promoting institutional change through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

GENDERACTIONplus aims to achieve the following impacts:

- Advance policy coordination among MS and AC countries and through stakeholder and citizen engagement.
- Improve research careers and working conditions in European R&I, by developing policy dialogue and solutions on inclusion and intersectionality, combatting gender-based violence, and promoting institutional changes through GEPs.
- Improve research quality and the social responsibility of knowledge by integrating the gender dimension into research and innovation (R&I).
- Reduce geographic inequality by targeting less experienced/engaged countries and regions.

1.2. Objectives of the report

GENDERACTIONplus builds on the work of WP3 in the GENDERACTION project (see Wroblewski 2021²). GENDERACTION argued that a meaningful set of indicators are key to supporting potential policy implementation. There is a risk of ineffective policy implementation and false conclusions if irrelevant indicators are used. GENDERACTIONplus WP5 builds on the framework for the monitoring of ERA Action 5 implementation at national level which has been developed in D5.1. The monitoring framework contains a set of indicators for the monitoring of ERA Action 5 implementation at national level which will serve as a basis to analyse policy implementation and progress towards gender equality in R&I. These indicators also address the current ERA policy agenda objectives – especially new topics like intersectionality, gender-based violence and the implementation of gender equality plans (GEPs) following the criteria formulated in the context of Horizon Europe.

Specifically, the second report of WP5 aims to

- analysing the implementation of ERA Action 5 at national level.
- formulating recommendations to increase the awareness regarding the relevance of a monitor for policy steering at national as well as European level.
- providing an input for mutual learning and capacity building activities focusing on using monitoring as a steering instrument to support policy implementation.

It is a challenge for WP5 that the current ERA policy agenda does not require the submission of a strategic policy document by Member States and Associated Countries. Hence, there are no comparable documents available as was the case for the previous ERA period. Therefore, the analysis is based on a survey among members of the ERA Forum subgroup on gender and inclusiveness conducted in spring 2024 as well as results of the benchmarking exercise conducted in WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6 and desk research.

1.3. The relationship of this report to other tasks and work packages

The work conducted in WP5 already served as an input for the webinar “Relevance of a national policy discourse in R&I” which took place in April 2023. The aim of the webinar was to discuss the relevance of a national policy discourse for the successful implementation of gender equality policies in R&I. The webinar was the first interaction with stakeholders (members of the policy CoP and the RFO CoP) to raise awareness for the relevance of monitoring and a policy discourse.

WP5 also contributed to a MLW on GEP impact and monitoring which took place in December 2023. The MLW was delivered through a joint collaboration between ISAS, SDU, UEFISCDI and WP5 and WP6 leaders in line with both the Policy CoP workplan as well as the results of the needs assessment survey and discussions in the Policy CoP meetings and WP7 meetings. The workshop was designed to cover the topics of indicators, monitoring and evaluation of gender equality, and was tied to Work Packages 5 and 6.

Furthermore, the policy recommendations of D5.2 will be discussed with the Policy CoP in November 2024.

² https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/GENDERACTION_WP3_final_report.pdf

1.4. Structure of the report

The second report of WP5 builds on the framework for a monitoring of ERA Action 5 implementation at national level and provides the analysis of ERA Action 5 implementation at national level. The report consists of four main parts:

- Firstly, the development of gender equality objectives in ERA is presented. For the current ERA period the governance structure is described.
- Secondly, the status quo regarding gender equality in ERA is described based on available statistics. In this section we also focus on missing data, particularly on the implementation of policies.
- Thirdly, the GENDERACTIONplus approach to monitoring is presented and the set of indicators is described.

Finally, the implementation of ERA Action 5 is analysed based on secondary data and survey data.

2. Gender Equality Objectives in the ERA

2.1. Gender Equality as a priority in the ERA

The political concept of the European Research Area (ERA) was first launched in 2000 with the publication of the European Commission's "Towards a European Research Area" Communication (EC 2000). The main objectives of this initiative were to boost Europe's competitiveness, to improve the coordination of research activities on both a national and a European level, to develop human resources and to increase the attractiveness of European research to the best researchers from all over the world. The EU's Framework Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration was considered to be the most important instrument for the implementation of the European Research Area.

In 2007, progress in the development of the ERA was assessed and new perspectives presented in the form of a Green Paper (EC 2007). The Green Paper underlines the importance of ERA for the European Union to become a leading knowledge society. It also confirmed the main ERA objectives. "The ERA concept encompasses three inter-related aspects: a European 'internal market' for research, where researchers, technology and knowledge can freely circulate; effective European-level coordination of national and regional research activities, programmes and policies; and initiatives implemented and funded at European level" (EC 2007: 5). In December 2008, the Competitiveness Council formulated a 2020 Vision for the European Research Area which was endorsed by the European Council (Council of the European Union 2008). The vision outlined of the ERA is based on six dimensions, namely: realising a single labour market for researchers; developing world-class research infrastructures; strengthening research institutions; sharing knowledge; optimising research programmes and priorities; and opening to the world through international cooperation in science and technology.

A third phase in the development of the ERA began in 2012 with the new Communication and Council Conclusions (EC 2012), which led to the adoption of the ERA Roadmap 2015-2020 (ERAC 2015). The purpose of the roadmap was to identify a limited number of top priority actions that will have the biggest impact on Europe's research and innovation whilst fully recognising that national research and innovation systems across Europe have different characteristics and specificities. It was up to the Member States to identify and decide which approaches to pursuing the ERA are most suited to the structures and dynamics of their own national research and innovation systems in the implementation of these actions (Council of the European Union 2015: 3). The ERA Roadmap also made provisions for monitoring in conjunction with ERA Progress Reports (for a critical discussion of this approach see Wroblewski 2021).

The ERA Roadmap 2015-2020 defined six priorities for policies to pursue ERA at national level:

- Priority 1 – Effective national research systems
- Priority 2a – Jointly addressing grand challenges
- Priority 2b – Making optimal use of public investments in research infrastructure
- Priority 3 – An open labour market for researchers
- Priority 4 – Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research
- Priority 5 – Optimal circulation and transfer of scientific knowledge
- Priority 6 – International cooperation.

Priority 4 defined three dimensions of gender equality: (1) the representation of women in science in general, (2) the representation of women in decision-making positions as well as structural and cultural barriers which lead to an underrepresentation of women in decision making, and (3) the integration of gender in research content. In the years that have followed since, the European Commission and the Council of the European Union refer to these dimensions of gender equality – e.g. in the Council Conclusions on the European Research Area Roadmap (2015) or in the recent ERA Progress Report (EC 2019).

The first dimension has already been addressed by the EC Communication “Women in Science” (EC 1999), a policy document which formulates the aim to “encourage women to take part in European research” (EC 1999: 3). The European Commission (EC) also envisaged the development of a coherent approach to increase the share of women in its Fifth Framework Programme (FP5, 1998-2002). This approach included the Marie Curie scholarships as well as corresponding advisory groups and assessment/monitoring panels aimed specifically at promoting research by, for and on women. In other words, its goal was not only to increase female participation in research but also to strengthen gender issues in research content (“research for women” and “research on women”). In the third phase of the development of the ERA (see, e.g. EC 2012; Council of the European Union 2012), the focus on gender in the ERA has been widened and formulated more explicitly. Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research is defined as one of six ERA priorities “to end the waste of talent which we cannot afford and to diversify views and approaches in research and foster excellence” (EC 2012: 4).

In September 2020 the European Commission launched the Communication “A New ERA for Research and Innovation” which reinforced its commitment to gender equality in order to strengthen the European R&I potential (EC 2020). The Council of the European Union also formulated a strong commitment to gender equality in R&I with its conclusions from December 2020 and May 2021. The Council conclusions focused on gender equality in the context of research careers as well as the development of inclusive gender equality plans at RPO level which also address the gender dimension in R&I. The Council defined the element of inclusiveness as a broad, gender-balanced and non-discriminatory participation of researchers and national and regional actors and R&I stakeholders across Europe in ERA activities. Furthermore, the first strategic plan for Horizon Europe considers gender equality as a crosscutting priority and foresees supporting actions strengthening the ERA through the promotion of inclusive gender equality (EC 2021b). In July 2021, a joint conference of the Slovenian Presidency of the Council of the EU and the European Commission funded project GENDERACTION took place which provided the opportunity to reflect on developments during the ERA period 2016-2020 and upcoming challenges regarding gender equality in R&I.³

In autumn 2021, the framework for the new ERA including a commitment to strengthen and further develop gender equality policies was approved by the Council of the European Union, the EC as well as MS and AC. An important element of this reinforced commitment to gender equality is represented by the **Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation**⁴ which was prepared by the two Presidency Trios (DE, PT, SI and FR, CZ, SE) and presented by the Slovenian Presidency to Member States in the Competitiveness Council of 28 September 2021. The Declaration reaffirms the

³ For a summary of the discussion see: https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/PR_DeepeningERA_Through_Gender_Equality.pdf

⁴ https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/PSEU/Ljubljana-Declaration-on-Gender-Equality-in-Research-and-Innovation- endorsed_final.pdf

commitment of the Member States and the European Commission to the implementation of gender equality and gender mainstreaming in the new ERA and outlines priority areas to be addressed to foster an inclusive ERA for all. The priority areas underlined by the Ljubljana Declaration are the following:

- Ensure fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths in research, and consider intersectional perspectives on gender inequalities;
- Facilitate mutual learning opportunities through form-follows-function robust governance;
- Employ existing and newly developed tools, such as Gender Equality Plans, to facilitate systemic institutional change and remove institutional barriers;
- Address and counteract gender-based violence;
- Support active monitoring and evaluation to ensure continuous improvement;
- Leverage synergies to enhance gender equality achievements within the ERA, but also within complementary fields such as the European Higher Education Area, Cohesion policy funds, innovation ecosystems, as well as in international cooperation;
- Underpinning the above priorities and activities, fully acknowledge gender mainstreaming as a horizontal principle.

With the Ljubljana Declaration, the main stakeholders in R&I (EC, MS/AC) agreed on the directions of further development: to address gender-based violence, to move from a gender oriented approach to an intersectional approach to gender equality, and to focus on GEPs as the most significant instrument to achieve sustainable progress towards gender equality in R&I. At the Competitiveness Council of 26 November 2021, the Ljubljana Declaration was endorsed by 25 of the 27 Member States, 11 other countries (including 10 Associated Countries or candidate countries), Switzerland and the European Commission. UK, Türkiye and Australia did not officially endorse the Declaration but expressed explicit support for it.

The **Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe**, which has been adopted by Member States, also formulates gender equality as a principle. The Council of the European Union approved the Pact for Research and Innovation and established the **ERA Policy Agenda** as the document which sets out the ERA actions. These actions are to be implemented jointly and voluntarily in a coordinated and flexible manner (Council of the European Union 2021a). The Pact for Research and Innovation as well as the ERA priorities set out in the Pact addresses challenges faced by EU and national R&I communities and society. In total, 18 ERA actions have been defined focusing on its implementation at the European and/or national level. The first ERA Policy Agenda (2022-2024) was approved by the Council as an Annex to the Council Conclusions on the Future Governance of the ERA on 26 November 2021 (Council of the European Union 2021b).

Each MS/AC expressed its commitment to the ERA actions in which they decide to participate. MS/AC were asked to express their commitment until 30 June 2022. The following ERA actions were defined (EC 2021a):

- Open Science including through EOSC (action 1)
- Copyright and data legislative framework (action 2)
- Research assessment (action 3)
- Promote active research careers (action 4)
- Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness (action 5)
- Academic freedom (action 6)
- Knowledge valorisation (action 7)

- Strengthen research infrastructures (action 8)
- Global approach (action 9)
- Missions and partnerships (action 10)
- Green transformation (action 11)
- Accelerate the green and digital transition (action 12)
- Empower higher education institutions (action 13)
- Bring science closer to citizens (action 14)
- Improve EU-wide access to excellence (action 16)
- Enhance public research institutions' strategic capacity (action 17)
- ERA monitoring (action 19)
- Future R&D investment (action 20)

Compared to the previous ERA period (2015-2020), ERA actions are more detailed and comprehensive than the priorities in the ERA roadmap. In the previous period, MS/AC were asked to define their concrete commitment in a national ERA roadmap (action plan) but it was expected that all six priorities were addressed. In the current ERA period, MS/AC involvement is formulated on a voluntary basis, but their commitment refers to a set of clearly defined expectations regarding the implementation of related actions. For example, action 5 “Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness, taking note of the Ljubljana Declaration” consists of eight sections description/background/rationale, main actors responsible for the implementation of the action, a timeframe and milestones, funding possibilities, expected impact, monitoring, communication and additional information. For ERA Action 5 four interlinked outcome deliverables are proposed (Council of the European Union 2021b: 16):

1. Develop a policy coordination mechanism to support all aspects of gender equality through inclusive Gender Equality Plans and policies, and a dedicated EU network on their implementation.
2. Strategy to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment in the European R&I system and to assure gender equality in working environments through institutional change in any research funding or performing organisation.
3. A policy approach to strengthen gender equality, that addresses gender mainstreaming to advance the new ERA.
4. Develop principles for the integration and evaluation of the gender perspective in research and innovation content in cooperation with national Research Funding Organisations.

By August 2022, the European Commission received written commitments to ERA actions from 26 Member States, four Associated Countries⁵, the Committee of the Regions and 17 stakeholder organisations (Council of the European Union 2022). 15 ERA actions passed the threshold defined in the Council Conclusions adopted in November 2021 (at least half of EU Member States support an ERA action).

⁵ Armenia, Georgia, Israel and Norway.

Action 4 (research careers and mobility) and action 8 (research infrastructures) received most support. Action 5 (gender equality and inclusiveness) was supported by 18 Member States, 2 Associated Countries and 9 stakeholder organisations.⁶

The following figure gives an overview of commitments by Member States to ERA actions in 2022.

Figure 1: Commitments by Member States to ERA actions in 2022

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	16	17	19	20	Total
Austria (AT)																			13
Belgium (BE)																			18
Bulgaria (BG)																			7
Croatia (HR)																			4
Cyprus (CY)																			11
Czechia (CZ)																			18
Denmark (DK)																			13
Estonia (EE)																			18
Finland (FI)																			11
France (FR)																			16
Germany (DE)																			18
Greece (EL)																			6
Hungary (HU)																			14
Ireland (IE)																			6
Italy (IT)																			14
Latvia (LV)																			8
Lithuania (LT)																			14
Luxembourg (LU)																			0
Malta (MT)																			5
Netherlands (NL)																			16
Poland (PL)																			11
Portugal (PT)																			18
Romania (RO)																			8
Slovakia (SK)																			10
Slovenia (SI)																			10
Spain (ES)																			17
Sweden (SE)																			10
Total	23	12	22	24	18	15	17	24	19	23	17	19	16	16	15	9	16	9	

Source: Council of the European Union 2022: 2.

⁶ Till Oktober 2024 22 Member States and three Associated Countries and 14 umbrella organisations signed up for ERA Action 5 (see [Register of Commission expert groups and other similar entities](#)).

2.2. ERA Governance

Through the Pact for R&I and the Council Conclusions on the future governance of ERA, the Council and the Commission jointly developed a new governance for ERA with new modes of collaboration. The aim was to create more effective structures in order to drive change, particularly through improved links between the European and national R&I policies and systems.

The **Council of Ministers** adopts or amends the ERA Policy Agenda and provides guidance on policy issues at ministerial level (Council Conclusions). Within the **ERA ministerial conference** in-depth discussions of specific ERA policies at ministerial level take place. The **European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC)** is a main actor in the ERA context (Council of the European Union 2021c). ERAC is a strategic policy advisory committee that advises the Council, the Commission and Member States on the full spectrum of research and innovation issues in the framework of the governance of the ERA, including current and future ERA Policy Agenda/ERA Actions as well as Framework Programmes. ERAC is co-chaired by the European Commission (Director-General or a deputy Director-General) and an elected representative from the Member States. The members of the Committee are the Member States and the European Commission. Representatives of countries associated to the R&I Union Framework Programme, as well as of relevant third countries, external experts and stakeholders may be invited to relevant ERAC meetings.

ESFRI⁷, EOSC⁸ Steering Board and Partnership Knowledge Hub⁹ support the steering of specific policies relevant for the ERA.¹⁰

⁷ <https://www.esfri.eu/>

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration>

⁹ https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-hub_en

¹⁰ ESFRI supports a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy-making on research infrastructures in Europe, and facilitates multilateral initiatives leading to the better use and development of research infrastructures, at EU and international level. The Competitiveness Council of November 2021 placed the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) at the top of the ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024 to enable the open sharing and reuse of research outputs. Partnership Knowledge Hub is intended to make the strategic coordinating process operational by establishing a formal structure for collaboration between the Commission and the authorities responsible for the national coordination and participation in EU R&I partnerships from Member States and Associated Countries.

Figure 2: ERA Governance

Source: ERA Portal Austria (www.era.gv.at)

The Council Conclusions on the future governance of the ERA of 26 November 2021 recognise the role of the ERA Forum as the body responsible for enhancing coordination towards the effective implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda, supporting the Commission and the Member States in the delivery of the ERA Actions. The ERA Forum is organised as a Commission expert group to which Member States and Associated Countries send representatives. The ERA Forum also involves stakeholder representatives in its work. The main tasks of the ERA Forum are the following:

- co-design and coordinate, between the Commission and the Member States, the preparation of Commission’s initiatives with regard to future updates of the ERA Policy Agenda, and discuss alignment with other policies;
- co-design and coordinate the implementation of the ERA Actions between the Commission, the Member States and, on a case-by-case basis, Associated Countries, stakeholders, as well as relevant third countries;
- analyse the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda through the ERA Scoreboard and the information provided through the ERA Policy Platform, and contribute to the Commission’s work in preparing a report to the Council;
- act as a facilitator for the preparation of additional candidate ERA Actions in variable geometry, with support from the Union where appropriate, as well as for the exchange of best practices on national ERA policies and measures.

The **ERA Forum** may establish subgroups to support the implementation of ERA Actions. To support the implementation of action 5 the **ERA Forum subgroup on inclusive gender equality** was established in spring 2023. Its crucial role is to communicate to and mobilise national constituencies as well as stakeholders, including umbrella organisations.

2.3. MS/AC committed to gender equality in R&I

With the Ljubljana Declaration, MS/AC recognise gender equality as a core EU value and gender mainstreaming as a core EU strategy. Furthermore, they acknowledge that Gender Equality Plans as the most significant instrument to achieve sustainable progress towards gender equality in R&I. The Ljubljana Declaration also formulates the need to better address gender-based violence in academic settings and to open gender equality policies to inclusiveness and intersections with other diversity categories and potential grounds for discrimination, such as ethnicity, disability and sexual orientation.

The following 36 countries (including 25 Member States) have endorsed the Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation: Albania, Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Montenegro, the Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Poland (Statement), Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

Not all Member States which endorsed the Ljubljana Declaration also expressed their commitment to ERA Action 5. In total 22 Member States and three other countries committed themselves to ERA Action 5: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Georgia (observer), Ireland, Israel (AC), Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, the Netherlands, Norway (AC), Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.

This commitment has been expressed by a written statement from MS/AC towards the European Commission. There is no requirement to formulate a concrete roadmap or action plan as in the previous ERA period (2015-2020). Nevertheless, some countries formulated a national action plan – see for example Austria (BMBWF/BMK 2022) or Germany (BMBF 2023). These documents are not currently accessible via a common platform.¹¹

¹¹ For the previous ERA period all documents were available on the ERA Portal Austria (<https://era.gv.at/>).

3. Available Information on Gender Equality in the ERA

The situation regarding gender equality in individual countries varies based on their experience with gender equality policies and the status quo in the different dimensions addressed by the ERA gender equality objectives (women’s representation in all fields and hierarchical levels, in decision-making, structural change, fostering the gender dimension in R&I content, counteracting gender-based violence including sexual harassment, intersectional approach). Assessment of the status quo regarding gender equality is not only difficult due to the complex gender equality constructs defined at the European level, but also because individual dimensions are interlinked and cannot be weighed against each other (e.g. that positive performance regarding women’s representation compensates for missing consideration of the gender dimension in R&I content). Similarly, the dimensions do not necessarily strengthen each other. For instance, a high share of women in Grade A positions does not inevitably foster improvement in how the gender dimension in R&I content is addressed. Another complicating factor is that comparable data is not available for all gender equality dimensions addressed by ERA Action 5. Several indicators are available which allow for a comparative analysis of women’s representation, while only a few indicators with a lower degree of validity are available for the gender dimension in R&I content. There is a further decline in the number of indicators relating to structural change or the prevalence of gender-based violence. Such indicators are currently not included in national statistics and when they are available, it is for selected countries in the framework of specific projects - such as the UniSAFE project¹² or GENDERACTIONplus (see the benchmarking reports of WP3 or WP6).

The *She Figures* (EC 2021c), the main source of EU wide comparable statistics on gender equality in R&I describe a differentiated picture of the status quo regarding gender equality in R&I which is not easy to interpret (see also Wroblewski 2021). The difficulties in interpreting available statistics stem, on the one hand, from the fact that indicators are usually interpreted without considering other dimensions. On the other hand, available statistics do not focus on the implementation of policies but on output dimensions (like the share of women in Grade A positions or among leaders of HEIs).

3.1. She Figures

Usually, gender equality in R&I is reduced to women’s representation – especially in top positions such as Grade A or HEI management. For instance, the ERA progress reports for the period 2015-2020 focused on the share of women in Grade A positions as the headline indicator. The share of female PhD graduates was used as an input indicator. Many *She Figures* indicators focus on women’s representation (see annex, Table 6). However, the picture that emerges from these indicators is inconsistent. Countries scoring high on one indicator do not necessarily score high on other indicators or across the board.

Focusing on the indicator share of women in Grade A positions, Romania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Latvia, Malta, Croatia, Lithuania and Bulgaria are top performers. In many (but not all) of these countries, the share of women in research is also above average. Romania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Latvia, Bulgaria, Croatia and Lithuania score highly in both indicators – share of women in research as well as the share of women in Grade A positions. Conversely, in Malta, the share of women in Grade A positions

¹² <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/national-reports/>

is above the EU average, but the share of women in research is below. In Estonia the share of women in research is above average but the share of women in Grade A positions is below average.

A different picture emerges when looking at the share of women as heads of higher education institutions. Countries with the highest share of women among leaders of higher education institutions are Latvia, Sweden, Iceland, Lithuania, Belgium, Denmark, Malta and Slovenia. The inconsistent pattern seems to be counterintuitive: one would expect a higher share of women among leaders of HEIs in countries with an almost gender balanced composition of professorships. The Glass Ceiling Index shows that this is not necessarily the case. The GCI measures the share of women in top positions (Grade A) compared to the share of women on the lower hierarchical levels and thus gives an indication of how difficult it is for women to reach top positions. The GCI is lowest in countries with a high share of women in Grade A positions – Malta, Bosnia Herzegovina, Romania or Bulgaria. However, not all of these countries have an above average share of women among leaders of HEIs – e.g. Romania. On the contrary, most countries with a low share of women in Grade A positions also have an GCI above average – e.g. Cyprus, Luxembourg, Belgium, Germany or Hungary. Among these, only Belgium has an above-average share of women among leaders of HEIs.

Therefore, it is not easy to interpret indicators focusing on women's representation in a coherent way. However, the situation becomes even more complex if we integrate the other dimensions of gender equality into the picture. There is little information available in relation to structural change in R&I. The 2018 volume of She Figures (EC 2019: 108) included the indicator "share of RPOs that adopted gender equality plans" (see Table 8 in annex). This information was derived from a survey which had been conducted in the context of the MORRI project in 2016. Compared to other data in She Figures, this information is less reliable due to survey nonresponse and is only available for the 2018 volume of She Figures. As a result of the introduction of the Horizon Europe GEP requirement in 2021 the situation has changed dramatically since then. However, in 2016 countries with above average shares of RPOs that adopted gender equality plans were Sweden, Germany, UK, Belgium France, Finland, Spain, Austria and Ireland. These countries had a legal GEP requirement for RPOs prior to 2021 (ERAC SWG on Gender in Research and Innovation 2021).

The third dimension – integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content – is represented in current She Figures by the percentage of a country's publications with a gender dimension in research and innovation content (based on bibliometric data from SCOPUS, covering a five-year period, 2014-2019). There is significant critique regarding the representativity of SCOPUS. For example, Tennant (2020) argues that SCOPUS and Web of Science are biased. "Both platforms are structurally biased against research produced in non-Western countries, non-English language research, and research from the arts, humanities, and social sciences" (Tennant 2020: 1). As women are overrepresented in the disciplines noted, this infers an additional gender bias. The indicators based on Horizon 2020 projects are also difficult to interpret as the success rates of countries (regarding applications for funding) vary in Horizon 2020 (European Court of Auditors 2022).

The She Figures have also been criticised for the lack of intersectional perspectives in relation to workforce statistics and also in relation to the gender dimension in research content. For the 2021 edition of She Figures an exploratory indicator has been developed to measure the integration of intersectional aspects in Horizon 2020 projects. This indicator analyses the text fields used for the indicator on gender dimension in R&I content in Horizon 2020 projects and combines the results retrieved with search queries on intersectional aspects on research (EC 2021d). This means that the gender dimension in

research content is represented by three indicators: the percentage of a country's publications with a gender dimension in research and innovation content, the percentage of Horizon 2020 projects in a country integrating a gender dimension or an intersectional approach (see annex, Table 7).

In summary, while the She Figures provide a wealth of information on the status quo and the development of gender equality in R&I, the interpretation of this information is not straightforward. There are several reasons for this: firstly, the challenge in interpreting the information arises from the complexity of the construct of gender equality. Secondly, the different dimensions of gender equality cannot all be represented with the same valency. And thirdly, there is currently no theoretical or political debate on how the different dimensions can and should be weighted in relation to each other. This would be a prerequisite for the development of a gender equality index that brings together the different dimensions.

3.2. Gender Equality Index (EIGE)

GENDERACTION D3.3 (Wroblewski 2021) has demonstrated that indicators commonly used to measure gender equality are not always adequate or meaningful. Wroblewski shows that the share of women in Grade A positions, which was referred to as the headline indicator in the ERA progress reports (EC 2019a; EC2019b), does not correlate with the EIGE gender equality index. The current data also does not show such a correlation. However, the EIGE gender equality index highly correlates with the national score in the innovation score board (Pearson 0.777). Figure 1 clearly shows that innovation leader countries (Sweden, Finland, Denmark, the Netherlands, Belgium) all score high on the EIGE gender equality index, followed by some of the strong innovator countries (Ireland, Luxembourg). Given this strong relationship it is regrettable that the European Innovation Scoreboard does not include any indicators on gender. This is justified by a lack of data. "The EIS does not include any indicators on gender as such data are not available for most of the indicators used to measure structural differences" (EC 2022: 12).

Figure 3: Correlation of EIGE Gender Equality Index and Summary Innovation Index

Source: EIGE GEI 2023/2023 (EIGE 2023), SII 2024 (EC 2024)

D3.3 also showed a high correlation of the share of RPOs with gender equality plans and the innovation score. This analysis is not replicated due to a lack of current data for the share of PROs with GEPs.

3.3. Information regarding the implementation of gender equality policies

As already mentioned, there is little information available on the implementation of gender equality policies (see above discussion regarding share of RPOs that implement GEPs). The GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking exercise provides data relating to the implementation of gender equality policies in countries/regions that participated in the survey. While this information does not cover all MS/AC, it remains an important data source due to a lack of EU wide statistics.

We know from different sources (SWG GRI survey and GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey) that 11 countries formulated a national GEP requirement and that two countries have other mechanisms in place which support GEP implementation. The GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey also collected information on the sectors the requirement applies to (public sector: higher education institutions, RPOs, administrative bodies; private sector: higher education institutions, RPOs, R&I companies). This information is available for seven countries only. In six countries not all sectors are addressed by the GEP requirement. Of the respondents, Sweden is the only country where the requirement applies to all sectors. All but one country with a GEP requirement also has related monitoring.

Table 1: GEP requirement at national level

GEP	Public sector			Private sector			National monitoring
	HEIs	RPOs	Admin.	HEIs	RPOs	R&I C.	
BE	Yes, BE-F; no BE-FWB						
BG	n.d.						
CZ	other						
DK	other						
DE	(yes)						
EE	(no)						
IE	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes
EL	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes
ES	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes
FR	(yes)						
HR	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes
IT	(no)						
CY	(no)						
LV	n.d.						
LT	no						
LU	n.d.						
HU	(no)						
MT	(no)						
NL	(no)						
AT	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no	no
PL	no						
PT	no						
RO	n.d.						
SI	(no)						
SK	no						
FI	(yes)						
SE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
UK	n.d.						
IS	(yes)						
NO	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
CH	(yes)						
TR	(no)						
BA	(no)						
IL	no						

Note: Admin= administrative bodies; R&I C = R&I Companies, yes/no/other mechanism – Source: GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey (2022, D6.1., p.13); (yes)/(no) – Source: SWG GRI survey (2021)

Only five countries and the Belgium Wallonia-Brussels Federation have policies in place which aim at promoting the gender dimension in research content. In most of the countries/regions that responded to the survey, such policies are implemented at RFO level.

Table 2: Countries with policies to strengthen the gender dimension in R&I content (national and RFO policies)

	national policies	RFO policies
BE	yes, BE-FWB; no, BE-F	yes, BE-FWB
BG	n.d.	yes
CZ	yes	yes
DK	no	no
DE	n.d.	n.d.
EE	n.d.	yes
IE	no	yes
EL	no	yes
ES	yes	yes
FR	n.d.	n.d.
HR	no	n.d.
IT	n.d.	yes
CY	n.d.	yes
LV	n.d.	n.d.
LT	no	yes
LU	n.d.	n.d.
HU	n.d.	n.d.
MT	n.d.	yes
NL	n.d.	n.d.
AT	yes	n.d.
PL	no	yes
PT	no	yes
RO	n.d.	yes
SI	n.d.	n.d.
SK	n.d.	n.d.
FI	n.d.	n.d.
SE	yes	yes
UK	n.d.	n.d.
IS	n.d.	n.d.
NO	yes	yes
CH	n.d.	n.d.
TR	n.d.	yes
BA	n.d.	n.d.
IL	no	n.d.

Source: GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey (2022, D4.1), own elaboration.

The situation is further fragmented when considering policies focusing on gender-based violence: only three countries already have national or regional policies targeting RFOs in place. Several countries are

planning to implement policies which address RPOs through actions led by RFOs. Nine countries have policies in place which directly address RPOs and require actions at institutional level.

Table 3: Countries with policies focusing on gender-based violence

	national/regional policies targeting RFOs	nat./reg. policies targeting RPOs with actions for RFOs	national/regional policies for RPOs with actions
BE	yes, BE-F; no BE-FWB	yes, BE-F; no BE-FWB	yes, BE-FWB; don't know, BE-F
BG	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
CZ	no	no	no
DK	no	no	no
DE	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
EE	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
IE	don't know	planned	yes
EL	yes	yes	yes
ES	no	no	yes
FR	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
HR	no	planned	don't know
IT	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
CY	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
LV	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
LT	yes	planned	yes
LU	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
HU	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
MT	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
NL	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
AT	planned	planned	yes
PL	yes	planned	yes
PT	don't know	yes	yes
RO	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
SI	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
SK	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
FI	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
SE	no	no	no
UK	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
IS	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
NO	don't know	no	yes
CH	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
TR	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
BA	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
IL	no	no	yes

Source: GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey (2022, D3.1, page 34).

These examples illustrate how fragmented the information regarding policy implementation is within Europe. This lack of comparable data not only complicates a comparative analysis between countries, it also makes it impossible to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of measures and thus reduces the possibility of mutual learning. A lack of empirical evidence to indicate what works, makes it difficult to identify good practices.

In response to this lack of evidence, GENDERACTIONplus aims to provide information on the implementation of policies in the framework of ERA Action 5. Monitoring ERA Action 5 implementation at national level would, on the one hand, provide MS/AC with a tool to support reflection on progress, success and failure of policies at national level. On the other hand, a comparative view on national monitoring would provide a basis for the European Commission to assess its approach to gender equality policy in ERA and to develop it further.

4. Monitoring Framework

The Pact for R&I (Council for the European Union 2021a) recommends the establishment of an enhanced ERA Monitoring Mechanism, to ensure a proper basis for evidence-informed policy-making in the ERA and to support and facilitate the implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda at both European and national levels. According to the Pact, the ERA Monitoring Mechanism should encompass the following elements:

- an ERA Scoreboard, which monitors progress towards the ERA objectives at Union level. The ERA Scoreboard should be updated regularly and should assess the overall consolidation and collective progress of ERA priorities. It should only display aggregated data at Union level.
- a more detailed ERA Dashboard monitoring progress towards the ERA objectives at national level, through a rich combination of relevant input, outcome and impact indicators and qualitative analyses that accommodate the different circumstances of Member States and that relate to the ERA priorities.
- regular policy dialogues between the Member States and the Commission – both bilaterally and multilaterally – to actively assess and guide the implementation of the ERA policy agenda, in particular through the sharing of best practices and mutual learning exercises. The Commission will provide further support through the Horizon Policy Support Facility and the Technical Support Instrument.
- an ERA policy online platform, where the Member States and the Commission should share information on their current and planned policies and programmes that contribute to implementing the ERA Policy Agenda.
- a review of the implementation of the ERA policy agenda by the Commission taking place every 18 months, including a report for consideration by the Council on the state of play of its implementation in view of steering the ongoing ERA Policy Agenda
- an annual report provided by the Commission to each Member State on its progress, in support of the regular policy dialogues between Member States and the Commission.

The GENDERACTIONplus approach to monitoring is described in the following section. Based on this, a proposal for a monitoring of ERA Action 5 implementation at national level is formulated. This proposal refers to the objectives and requirements formulated in the strategic ERA documents (EC 2020; EC 2021a, 2021b; Council of the European Union 2021a).

4.1. Aim and purpose of a monitoring

For the purposes of this report, we define monitoring in line with the definition proposed by Markiewicz and Patrick (2016: 12) as: “the planned, continuous and systematic collection and analysis of program information able to provide management and key stakeholders with an indication of the extent of progress in implementation, and in relation to program performance against stated objectives and expectations”¹³.

¹³ This does not include a systematic determination of the quality and value of the policies or measures implemented or their contribution to the achievement of goals and objectives, which would be the task of an evaluation.

Continuous monitoring generally pursues four goals which together support the efficient use of resources (see also Wroblewski 2021):

- Monitoring should provide an overview of current developments in the context of the policy of interest. In the context of gender equality in ERA, relevant indicators refer to the number of higher education institutions (HEIs) and the development in the total number of professors and researchers. This information is necessary to interpret the monitoring indicators.
- The core function of monitoring is to provide information about policy implementation (e.g. number of policies implemented, number of participants in training programmes and share of women, number of beneficiaries of subsidies and share of women, budget spent on specific measures). This information makes accountability of stakeholders transparent and provides first indications of suboptimal implementation.
- In an ideal case, the indicators used in a monitoring system also provide the basis for policy steering. This would require that targets for specific policies are formulated in a way that corresponds to the indicator(s) (e.g. when the performance agreement between a government ministry and a university contains the target to increase the share of women in professorships, and the monitoring includes a corresponding indicator).
- The information provided by the monitoring helps to identify deviations from planned implementation and consequently the need to adapt policies or their implementation at an early stage.

Efficient monitoring should be based on the following principles (see also Wroblewski et al. 2017).

- In general, monitoring systems are **based on empirical data** which is easily accessible and available on a regular basis. In most cases, monitoring indicators consist of quantitative indicators which are derived from the main objectives in a policy field. However, objectives cannot always be formulated in a quantifiable manner. In such cases, qualitative indicators should be included.
- A monitoring system should include **indicators which describe the context** of the policy or measure, the **expected output or outcome** of a policy as well as its **implementation**. Examples of context indicators in the field of national gender equality policy in R&I are the numbers of male and female researchers or the number of research institutions. An example of an indicator which describes the expected output is the share of women among newly-appointed professors. Potential outcome indicators are the share of female professors or the share of women in decision-making bodies.
- Indicators focusing on the implementation of policies should represent the number of participants in programmes, the budget spent on programme implementation, or the number of complaints addressed to an equality officer. Indicators focusing on the implementation of policies should be derived from a logic model or a programme theory explicitly formulated for the concrete policy.¹⁴
- Monitoring indicators should be developed with the participation of the main stakeholders. The aim is to establish an **agreed set of indicators** which all relevant stakeholders accept as

¹⁴ A logic model should indicate the goal of a policy (intended impact), then the changes (outcomes) that need to be made to achieve that goal, then all the things that need to be delivered (outputs) to bring about those changes and the activities that need to be carried out in order to ensure that the planned outputs are delivered. For further information, see W.K. Kellogg Foundation (2004).

meaningful and relevant. This agreed set of indicators should likewise be based on a data source which all stakeholders define as reliable.

- The agreed set of **indicators** should be **available at regular intervals** (e.g. yearly or monthly). The timing should be linked to the planned intervals for presentation and discussion of monitoring results (e.g. in the form of annual or monthly reports).
- Monitoring results should be **presented and interpreted on a regular basis**. This presentation will both contribute to a gender equality discourse in the concrete policy field and provide the basis for policy learning. Monitoring results allow the overall political strategy and the concrete policy design to be reviewed. They also facilitate the assessment of progress towards the planned outcome. If deviations from the expected outcome are identified, an analysis of the underlying mechanisms and causes should be carried out. Lessons learned (success stories as well as failures) should also be identified.
- Finally, a monitoring system should be seen as a **“living tool”** which has to be adapted when policies are changed.

4.2. Monitoring as part of a complete policy cycle and embedded in a policy discourse

D3.3 of GENDERACTION (Wroblewski 2021) stressed the relevance of a common understanding of gender equality challenges and objectives as well as a common understanding of progress towards gender equality as central elements of a policy discourse which should be developed at the European and the national level. We understand discourse to be “thematically connected and problem-related semiotic (for example oral or written) occurrences that relate to specific semiotic types, which serve particular political functions” (Reisigl 2008: 99; see also Wodak 2008). Hence, we start from the position that problems are not given but rather social constructs (see Bacchi 2009). This means that “gender equality”, “gender-based violence” or “intersectionality” are discursively constructed forms of social knowledge. ERA Action 5 policies are part of this productive process, for example with regard to the way the problem of gender inequality is presented and which types of solutions are proposed (Bacchi 2000). This is why we focus in our analysis of the implementation of ERA Action 5 on the gender equality objectives formulated as well as measures implemented.

A national discourse on gender equality in R&I aims at securing a common understanding of the status quo of gender equality (where do we stand?), of challenges to be addressed (what are our priorities?) and objectives to be reached (what do we want to achieve?). This requires the involvement of a broad range of stakeholders. If we take the perspective of a national authority, it is important to have a common understanding within the organisation as well as a shared understanding with other relevant national authorities and ministries to avoid a situation that other policies pursued contradict gender equality objectives or to secure that synergies are used. Furthermore, it is important to have a shared understanding with those designing and implementing concrete measures and those who are addressed by these measures.

Furthermore, GENDERACTIONplus is based on the assumption that the effective implementation of policies follows a complete policy cycle. Ideally, gender equality policies begin from a baseline

assessment of the status quo regarding gender equality. What are the main challenges to be addressed? Which mechanisms produce inequalities? How could these inequalities be tackled? Based on the results of the gender analysis, gender equality objectives are formulated. These objectives are the starting point for the development of concrete measures. These measures are implemented, monitored and, in an ideal world, evaluated.

Figure 4: Complete cycle for the development and implementation of gender equality policies

Source: own elaboration based on May, Wildavsky 1978

This ideal model can be formulated for the European level as well as the national, regional¹⁵ or institutional level. Ideally, the levels influence and strengthen each other. This means that the objectives formulated or measures taken at the European level are adopted at the national level or, if necessary, adapted to the national circumstances. Similarly, the national gender equality objectives are adopted at the institutional level or priorities for gender equality are set according to the respective framework conditions. In this ideal world described, the national goals would not contradict those at EU level, nor would the institutional goals contradict those at national level. Any reservations or resistance are raised and discussed in a corresponding policy discourse.

¹⁵ In the following, the focus is on the national level in order to reduce complexity. If the regional level plays a central role in policymaking, it should always be taken into account as an intermediate level.

Figure 5: Interplay between EU, national and institutional gender equality objectives and policies

Source: own elaboration.

In this ideal model, the understanding of the problem and the objectives are agreed on and do not change on the following level. However, in most cases, the reality differs from this ideal model. And this is very similar on both the national level and the institutional level.

In an ideal case, a national or institutional policy is based on a gender analysis which provides an assessment of the status quo regarding gender equality. Results of the gender analysis serve as the basis for the definition of gender equality objectives. This decision is in most cases a top-down decision – in some cases based on a participatory approach (by involving stakeholders). What we then see is a phenomenon of down-sourcing the responsibility for reaching these goals. Within the organisation, units or departments become responsible for the development and implementation of gender equality measures within the framework of the defined objectives. At national level, the development and implementation of concrete measures is sometimes outsourced – experts or stakeholders are commissioned with this task. As such, in the implementation of a complete policy cycle we see a change of the strategic level. With this change of strategic level, we cannot assume that the perception of the problem and the interpretation of the problem remain stable. When objectives are defined in a broad and vague way – more as a general commitment than a concrete objective – a broad range of interpretations become possible.

What we also see in several cases is a missing link of the level of policy implementation back to the top-down level. Particularly, when monitoring and evaluation are not standard tools of policy making, there is a lack of discussion of experiences of the implementation of measures and the results achieved. A national discourse should also focus on the discussion of what worked, why or why not and what lessons were learned for future policies.

Figure 6: Incomplete policy cycle

Source: own elaboration.

4.3. Level of monitoring

A monitoring of policy implementation and the related discourse can focus on the European, the national or the institutional level. At each level, effective policy implementation requires a participatory approach – regarding the development and implementation of policies as well as regarding monitoring. In an ideal case, the different levels are interlinked and refer to each other. For example, the use of synergies or potential leverage effects between the European and national level is possible when national gender equality policies refer to European objectives and policies. Synergies may result from the fact that European policies as well as national policies address research performing organisations (RPOs). If RPOs are exposed to divergent requirements, uncertainties, parallel and unrelated initiatives or – in a worst case – frustrations may occur. A concrete example is the GEP requirement formulated by Horizon Europe (European level), which is not necessarily linked to national policies. As a consequence, institutions may be confronted with divergent standards at European and national level, how GEPs should look like and which criteria they should meet.

In an ideal setting, gender equality policies at different levels pursue the same objectives and related monitoring are based on comparable indicators. The congruence of objectives and approaches at European and national level is also the result of a common gender equality policy discourse.

The monitoring outlined in the following focuses on the national level. The main question is how to represent progress in policy implementation in a monitoring. This is not a synonym to the monitoring of

the development of gender equality indicators (e.g. share of women in Grade A positions or in HEI top management).

4.4. Indicators to monitor ERA Action 5 implementation

To assess the implementation of ERA Action 5 a set of qualitative indicators is proposed which will complement the analysis of gender equality based on quantitative indicators such as She Figures (see section 3).

Qualitative indicators are proposed for the following dimensions:

Commitment to gender equality and inclusiveness

- Endorsement of the Ljubljana Declaration (yes/no)
- Commitment to ERA Action 5 (yes/no)
- Formulation of a national action plan (ERA NAP) (yes/no)
- Formulation of a national policy on gender equality focusing on R&I and/or HEIs which refers to ERA

Gender Equality Objectives

- Are objectives formulated focusing on fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)
- Are objectives formulated focusing on systemic institutional and structural change? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)
- Are objectives formulated to ensure gender balance and increase diversity in decision-making? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)
- Are objectives formulated to foster the integration of sex, gender and intersectional analysis into research and innovation content? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)
- Are objectives formulated focusing on counteracting gender-based violence including sexual harassment? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)
- Are objectives formulated focusing on removing inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation? (yes/no, if yes: which concrete objectives are formulated)

Gender equality measures planned and implemented

- Are measures planned/implemented to promote fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).
- Are measures planned/implemented to promote systemic institutional and structural change? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).
- Are measures planned/implemented to promote gender balance and increase diversity in decision-making? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).
- Are measures planned/implemented to promote the integration of sex, gender and intersectional analysis into research and innovation content? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).
- Are measures planned/implemented to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).

- Are measures planned/implemented to remove inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation? (yes, planned/yes, implemented/no, if yes: description of measure(s)).

Monitoring of policy implementation

- Does a monitoring for gender equality exist which provides information on relevant gender equality dimensions like women's representation in all fields and hierarchical levels, women's participation in decision-making, gender dimension and intersectional approaches in research and innovation content, prevalence of gender-based violence including sexual harassment? If yes, which concrete indicators are covered by the monitoring and is the monitoring publicly accessible?
- Does a monitoring exist which focuses on the implementation of national measures (e.g. number of participants in trainings or programmes funded by national authorities, budget spent)? (yes/no, if yes: description of information provided)
- Does a monitoring exist which focuses on the implementation of national or European policies by RPOs and RFOs (e.g. number of institutions with a GEP)? (yes/no, if yes: description of information provided)

For countries participating in the GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey, some of the information relevant for a monitoring of ERA Action 5 implementation described above is available. For a monitoring covering all MS/AC committed to ERA Action 5, it is necessary to complement the information available. The relevant information cannot be obtained from policy documents such as national ERA Action Plans or national strategies focusing on gender equality in R&I and/or HEIs, as these documents are not available for all countries in a comparable way. To compensate for this lack of information, a questionnaire (see Annex 2) has been distributed among members of the ERA Forum subgroup on gender and inclusiveness in spring 2024.¹⁶

In total 19 countries participated in the survey – 17 Member States (AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, ES, FI, FR, IE, LT, LU, NL, PL, PT, SI, SE, SK) and two Associated Countries (IL, NO). In light of this, it is pertinent to highlight that the ten countries which did not participate in the survey, with the exception of Italy and Greece, are all classified as younger Member States (acceding from 2004 onwards). As such, the survey is therefore more likely to mirror the situation of EU14¹⁷ countries and has limited significance for the newer Member States.

¹⁶ WP5 would like to express its gratitude to Marcela Linkova for her invaluable assistance in the implementation of the survey, in particular, in disseminating the questionnaire and providing multiple individual reminders to members who had not responded.

¹⁷ Former EU15 countries without UK.

5. Implementation of ERA Action 5 at national level

5.1. Gender equality strategy

Six member states and two associated countries formulated an ERA action plan for the period 2022-2024 (BE, DE, LU, AT, FI, LT, IL, NO). Three countries did not formulate an ERA action plan but have a national or regional policy on gender equality focusing on HEI or R&I (PT, CZ, SI) which refers to ERA. Four countries have both policy documents in place (an ERA action plan and a national or regional policy; BE, LU, LT, IL). Among survey respondents, eight countries neither have an ERA action plan nor a national or regional policy in place (FR, NL, DK, ES, SE, PL, SK, IE).

Unfortunately, not all ERA action plans are available online and in English (e.g. the German or the Norwegian action plan is only available in national language).

The **Austrian ERA action plan 2022-2025** takes up all the topics addressed in ERA Action 5. In concrete, the following meta goals are formulated: “Overall, it is important to strengthen the general commitment to gender equality, especially at management level, to ensure suitable framework conditions (e.g. resources in the institutions), to prioritise and optimise the impact of the measures, and to call on and support all relevant actors in science and research to actively take on society's gender equality mandate” (BMBWF/BMK 2022: 25).

Within this meta goal the Austrian ERA action plan formulates the following concrete goals: (1) Support for higher education and research (funding) institutions in the creation, further development and implementation of their equality plans (2) Development of guidelines regarding the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content as well as in research-led teaching, for application in the context of research funding, amongst others. (3) Contributions to raising awareness and making gender-based violence and sexual harassment visible in higher education and research (funding) institutions, as well as developing measures to prevent or combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment. (4) Initiation and promotion of a cross-sectoral gender equality dialogue, among other things, to further develop existing gender equality concepts and measures towards intersectionality and diversity.

In **Belgium**, the strategic documents addressing gender equality have been formulated by RFOs at regional (FNRS and FWO) and the national level (BELSPO). In concrete the Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.–FNRS) formulated the Plan D’Egalité de Genre (2022-2025)¹⁸ and the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO) formulated a Gender Equality Plan (GEP)¹⁹ which refers to the European Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Furthermore, the Research Programme Service of the Federal Science Policy (BELSPO) has a GEP in place.

The **German action plan** (BMBF 2023) does not contain a specific chapter on gender equality. As part of action area 5, which pertains to the strengthening of participation in the research and innovation system, the objective is to increase the proportion of women in the science system, particularly in management positions. In order to achieve this, it is planned to continue the programme for female professors.

¹⁸ <https://www.frs-fnrs.be/docs/Plan-egalite-genre-FNRS-2022.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://www.fwo.be/media/b4kfnhim/gender-equality-plan.pdf>

In **Luxembourg** the government has changed in 2023 and in spring 2024 it was planned to develop a new ERA action plan 2024-2026. In spring 2023 an agreement of the governmental coalition has been available which formulates a general commitment to set actions in the following fields: government, decision making, employment and salaries, information and media, gender-based violence.²⁰ The university of Luxembourg, the only university in Luxembourg, formulated a gender equality policy 2021-2025.²¹ Research Luxembourg has specific guidelines on gender equality, collecting and monitoring gender disaggregated data and recruitment.²² Furthermore, the only RFO in Luxembourg, FNR, formulated an action plan on gender, equality, diversity, and inclusion for 2022 to 2024.²³

In 2023, the **Finnish government** adopted a statement on promoting equality, gender equality and non-discrimination in Finnish society.²⁴ The commitment to promote gender equality is based on a report on the state of equality and diversity in Finnish higher education institutions and its recommendations (KOTAMO report, Ministry of Education and Culture 2022).

In **Lithuania**, the ministry for science and research integrates ERA related activities into various national measures (but a separate umbrella ERA action plan is not prepared). The Ministry's 2022-2030 development program "Strengthening the Innovation Ecosystem in Science Centres" includes the measure "Support for activities aimed at implementing the priorities of the European Research Area, in order to achieve institutional changes²⁵".

In **Israel**, the "Multiyear Plan for Gender Fairness in Academia" has been formulated.²⁶ The plan contains scholarship for women post-doctoral students (with a specific focus on women in high-tech fields), prizes for institutions which successfully implement gender equality policies and a special budget for advisors on gender fairness at HEIs. Furthermore, for the first time, academic institutions are asked to publish an annual gender report on their website in accordance with the regulations of the European Union.

The **Norwegian** ERA action plan 2022-2024²⁷ foresees three priorities regarding the implementation of ERA Action 5: to support GEPs at institutional level, to continue and further develop the gender balance programme in the Norwegian Research Council and to strengthen the gender dimension in research and innovation.

²⁰ <https://mega.public.lu/content/dam/mega/fr/societe/politique-niveau-national/Extrait-MEGA-accord-de-coalition-2018-2023.pdf>

²¹ <https://www.uni.lu/en/about/gender-equality/policy/#focus-policy>

²² <https://www.researchluxembourg.org/en/research-landscape/gender-equality/>
<https://www.researchluxembourg.org/en/collecting-and-monitoring-gender-disaggregated-data/>
<https://www.researchluxembourg.org/en/research-landscape/gender-equality/gender-equality-policy-talent-attraction-fair-recruitment/>

²³ <https://www.fnr.lu/fnr-gender-equality-plan/>

²⁴ https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/165112/VN_Statement_31082023_EN.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

²⁵ No strategic document provided.

²⁶ <https://che.org.il/en/the-new-multiannual-program/multi-annual-plan-for-gender-fairness-in-academia/>

²⁷ In Norwegian only:

<https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/7903662193364452b11aaf27fcc96d88/no/pdfs/nasjonal-handlingsplan-for-europeiske-forskingsomr.pdf>

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy 2021 – 2030 (Office of the Government of the Czech Republic 2021) refers to ERA Action 5 in chapter 8 “Knowledge”. In concrete, three strategic objectives are formulated: (1) To ensure the maximum development potential of girls and boys, and men and women, (2) Expanding the content of education, science and research by a gender perspective and (3) Applying the gender aspect in operation and in the management of education and science/research institutions.

In **Portugal**, the main RFO (FCT) launched the RESTART Programme²⁸, a funding instrument which aims at promoting gender equality and opportunities through the competitive funding of individual R&D projects. RESTART is strongly impacting women researchers in their early careers, parental leaves entail additional challenges, from the scientific production, to funding, to the timeline and planning of careers. The Programme was launched in February 2023, and already had a second call in 2024.

Slovenia did not formulate a separate ERA action plan since ERA actions are fully incorporated into the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030, the Action Plan for the Implementation of the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030 and the Action Plan on Gender Equality in R&I (as part of the National Action Plan on Gender Equality in Slovenia).

5.2. Gender equality objectives

Respondents were asked if there are specific gender equality objectives formulated for the national or regional level. 16 countries mention the objective to achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths and 15 pursue the objective to achieve systemic institutional and structural change (e.g. by supporting the uptake of (inclusive) GEPs). The objective to achieve gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making is mentioned by 14 countries, the objective to reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation is stated by 13 countries and the objective to achieve integration of sex, gender and/or intersectional analysis into research and innovation content is pursued by 12 countries (see also Table 11 in Annex).

²⁸ <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/outros-apoios/programa-restart/>

Table 4: Countries with gender equality objectives formulated at national level

Objectives to	Number of countries	In % of responding countries
... achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths	16	84%
... achieve systemic institutional and structural change, i.e. supporting the uptake of (inclusive) gender equality plans	15	79%
... achieve gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making	14	74%
... achieve integration of sex, gender and/or intersectional analysis into research and innovation content	12	63%
... counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment	15	83%
... reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation	13	68%

Source: GENDERACTIONplus survey 2024.

In the following sections an overview is provided, where concrete objectives have been formulated. Where applicable, the information is included if the objective is based on legislation or integrated into a specific strategy.

5.2.1. Objectives to achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths

Sixteen responding countries formulated a specific objective to achieve **fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths** at national/regional level. These are not always directly mentioned in the strategic documents mentioned above.

In **Austria**, a working group of the Austrian Higher Education Convention institutions developed recommendations and concrete measures to support attractive and sustainable careers for researchers. These measures also included a reform of the evaluation system for scientists and researchers. In these recommendations gender equality is considered as a crosscutting topic. Furthermore, objective 3 of the Austrian RTI-Strategy²⁹ (Knowledge, talents and skills) aims at strengthening gender equality and diversity in R&D and enhancing the attractiveness and promotion of research careers, particularly for women, by intensifying equal opportunity programmes and measures in human resources and career planning.

Belgium aims at strengthening equal opportunities in hiring and promotions; work life balance; diverse promotion committees and juries; action against GBV, women in leadership positions; creating working groups to monitor and report on this. VLIR (Flanders) established a working group on diversity and an

²⁹ https://era.gv.at/public/documents/4489/RTI_Strategy_2030-1-1.pdf

ad-hoc working group on gender-based violence. At FNRS (RFO for the French speaking community) the Comité Femmes et Sciences; Commission genre dans l'enseignement supérieur is also working on the topic.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy aims at "increasing the quality and transparency of HR management at universities and research institutions" through "supporting the implementation of Gender Equality Plans at RDI institutions" and "taking into account quality and transparency of HR in evaluating targeted aid projects by documenting a high quality and transparent institutional solution to HR development and gender equality".

The **German** ERA Action Plan comprises the objective to further increase the proportion of women in science towards parity, in particular in leadership positions. To achieve this, structural and cultural change in science and research is needed and is supported by the Programme for Women Professors of the Federal Government and the Länder.

In **Denmark** the Equal Opportunities Act states that public authorities (including universities and other research organisations) shall seek to promote gender equality and incorporate gender equality in all planning and administration within their scope.

The second **Irish** Review of Gender Equality (HEA 2022a) formulated a number of recommendations related to career development and precarity. Higher Education Institutions are expected to include relevant actions in their GEPs or gender equality work to address these challenges.

In **France**, public institutions have to elaborate and implement gender equality plans since 2019. The Decree n°2020-528 of 4 May 2020 defines the requirements of elaboration and implementation of professional gender equality in public service and indicates that public institutions have to implement strategies and measures to ensure equal career opportunities. In addition, they should define objectives, indicators and an implementation timetable.

In **Portugal**, the aim to promote gender equality in research activities and careers is addressed by the RESTART Programme (see above).

The **Spanish** law on R&I is aligned with the European framework and aims at supporting institutional change to create inclusive and gender-sensitive environments i.e., free from gender bias, discrimination, sexist behaviour and sexual harassment.

In **Finland**, the KOTAMO project (2021-22) has been commissioned to examine the state of equality, non-discrimination and diversity among teaching and research staff in Finnish higher education institutions and to propose recommendations for measures to address the problems identified. The study focused on gender equality and ethnic diversity. The report gives recommendations for higher education institutions to achieve open and equal requirement processes. Currently, the employees' organisations of the higher education sector are launching a joint project to prepare operating method recommendations for equal recruitment and the preparation of salary surveys.

In **Sweden**, the objective of increasing the number of female professors has been in place since 1997 and remains a priority.

The newly established **Slovak** Institute for IT Research Careers (KINIT) considers gender and inclusiveness when providing services for companies.

In **Lithuania**, criteria for project funding include the criterion that the project contributes directly to the implementation of equal opportunities and non-discrimination. Furthermore, the initiative "Support for activities intended to implement the priorities of the European Research Area for institutional changes" was launched. Under this initiative, RPO can apply for up to € 60,000 funding to implement ERA actions activities (the initiative covers ERA actions 3, 4, 5, 9, 11, 12, 13, and 14).

In the **Netherlands**, universities are working on valuing different kinds of career paths for their staff members. It is assumed that this will also support gender equality, because not just one type of career path will be valued. One concrete objective of the initiative is to enable more diversity in career paths and profiles for academics.³⁰

Israel is monitoring women's advancement in higher positions in academia. Furthermore, an index has been developed to show if universities meet the goals they set for themselves which also covers gender objectives.

Norway formulated a research career strategy³¹ which contains concrete objectives and considers gender equality as a crosscutting issue.

5.2.2. Objectives to achieve systemic institutional and structural change

Fifteen countries formulated a concrete objective to support systemic institutional or structural change. In most cases this objective is linked to the Horizon Europe GEP requirement.³²

The **Austrian** ERA action plan contains the objective to establish a coordination structure for the (further) development and implementation of equality plans at Austrian higher education and research (funding) institutions.

In the **Belgian** case, a reference is made to GEPs, which are now in place in all universities and in the main funding organisations (FNRS and FWO). These GEPs contain procedures for hiring, promoting as well as regulations regarding training and monitoring.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy includes the aim to "increase the quality and transparency of HR management at universities and research institutions" through "supporting the implementation of Gender Equality Plans at RDI institutions". To this end, a grant provided by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports funds support services provided by the Centre for Gender and Science at the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences relate to institutional change through GEPs (consultations, training, Community of Practice titled Community for Change, e-learning Moodle course, guides and handbooks).

The **German** ERA Action Plan aims at strengthening equal opportunities (which includes structural and cultural change) by the Programme for Women Professors of the Federal Government and the Länder.

³⁰ <https://recognitionrewards.nl/>

³¹ <https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/f14b4981c2f549489941bc607cf9bc5f/strategy-for-the-recruitment-and-career-development-of-young-researchers.pdf>

³² Luxembourg did not provide additional information on this objective.

In the **Danish** case, a reference is made to the tripartite agreement on sexual harassment from 2022 (see below). The implementation of measures based on the agreement also initiate institutional and structural change.

In **Ireland**, all publicly funded HEIs participate in the Athena Swan Ireland Charter³³ which requires the development and implementation of an inclusive GEP. Compliance with set timelines for engagement with the Athena Swan Ireland Charter is also required for institutional eligibility for research funding from national agencies.

In **France**, most GEPs have integrated an axis focused on the accountability of the governing level of RPOs to ensure systemic, institutional, and structural change, and the sustainability of gender equality plans. Moreover, the law imposes financial penalties to public institutions that fail to elaborate a GEP.

Portugal did not formulate concrete objectives regarding systemic institutional and structural change as most RPOs and RFOs have had their GEP in place since 2022.

The **Spanish** law on R&I (2022) is in line with the EU framework and aims at supporting institutional change to support inclusive and gender-sensitive environments, i.e., free from gender bias, discrimination, sexist behaviour and sexual harassment.

In **Finland**, HEIs are obliged to promote equality and non-discrimination in their operations, as well as to draw up and maintain plans for their promotion in line with [?] Law on equality between women and men, 1986/609 and Equality Act, 1325/2014.

In **Sweden**, the government has assigned R&I institutions the responsibility for gender mainstreaming, including the formulation of plans for this work.

The **Lithuanian** Labour Code sets out the requirements for employers to implement gender equality measures. Furthermore, the ministry has launched the initiative "Support for activities intended to implement the priorities of the European Research Area for institutional changes" under which RPOs can apply for up to € 60,000 funding to implement ERA actions activities (including institutional and structural change).

For the **Netherlands**, the National Action Plan for Greater Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education and Research contains the objective "bring together and support institutional diversity plans, enabling more cooperation". To achieve this, a guide was developed.³⁴ The guide follows the recommendations of the European Commission and provides suggestions, examples and best practices for drawing up gender equality plans.

In **Israel**, each academic institution that participates in the aforementioned index sets gender equality goals and is evaluated based on its ability to achieve them. This is a prerequisite for receiving the financial incentive from the Israeli Council for Higher Education (CHE), which is financed by the PBC, Planning and Budgeting Committee.

³³ <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/international-charters/athena-swain-ireland>

³⁴ <https://www.dihoo.eu/documents/publications/2021/06/15/guide-for-drawing-up-gender-equality-plans>

The **Norwegian** ERA Action plan formulates the objective to support gender equality plans at institutional level as well as to monitor the development and implementation of GEPs at institutional level.

5.2.3. Objectives to achieve gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making

Fourteen countries are committed to the objective to achieve gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making.³⁵ However, the focus lies on gender balance.

Belgian RFOs formulate concrete objectives in the context of gender balance. FNRS aims at appointing 50 % women in leadership positions. VLIR aims at diversity in representation in commissions and councils. The FWO strives to include at least 40 % of the under-represented gender in its expert panels, considering the composition by gender of the groups of researchers from which experts can be recruited; at least one-third of the Board of Trustees should be of the under-represented gender.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy contains a chapter on equality in decision making, however, it does not contain any specific aims or measures in relation to the research sector.

For **Germany**, again a reference is made to the Programme for Women Professors of the Federal Government and the Länder.

In **Denmark**, according to the Equal Opportunities Act, all public boards, councils etc. should be gender balanced.

National requirements for **Irish** HEIs include gender balance on key decision-making committees and structures. HEIs provide data on the gender composition of key committees to the national authority. HEIs are also expected to have a member of the senior executive/Management team with responsibility for EDI, ideally in the role of Vice-President for EDI.

In **France**, the Sauvadet Law introduced gender quotas in senior executive positions in the State bureaucracy in 2012 (Jacquemart et al. 2020). Moreover, the Fioraso law, which applies specifically to the HE sector, included provisions to promote parity in university decision-making bodies and representative bodies. The Rixain Law of 2021 reinforced parity in recruitment panels for higher education access, and also imposes quotas in executive positions of large companies, requiring 40 % of women in senior management by 2030, with financial penalties for non-compliance.

Portugal considers GEPs as important vehicles for gender balance in decision making. Diversity objectives are not yet clearly embedded in GEPs, or at least no detailed information is available. The National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination (ENIND) has defined the following targets: (1) to increase the share of women in the management and governance bodies of HEIS from 43 % (2017) to 50 % (2030); (2) to increase the share of women researchers with R&D activities from 43 % (2017) to 50 % (2030), (3) to increase the share of associate professors, principal coordinators and full professors from 30 % (2016) to 50 % (2030), (4) to support the feminisation of higher education's degrees in ICT from 18.5 % (2015) to 33.3 % (2030) and (5) to sensitize HEIs to integrate the gender perspective and the gender stereotype deconstruction in graduates and master degrees.

³⁵ Luxembourg did not provide additional information on this objective.

For **Slovenia**, the objective is anchored in the Scientific Research and Innovation Act, the Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy and the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act.

The **Spanish** law on R&I (2022) includes affirmative action measures to advance women to the highest levels of the research career.

In **Sweden**, equal representation (gender) on boards and other decision-making bodies in R&I is a legal requirement that has been in place since the early 2000s.

In **Lithuania**, RPOs are incentivised to follow ERA targets by the initiative "Support for activities intended to implement the priorities of the European Research Area for the purpose of institutional changes". RPOs can apply for financial support to implement ERA Action 5.

In the **Netherlands**, the government set objectives to ensure gender balance in decision making in the (semi) public sector in 2022. Organisations in this sector have to set a target figure of at least 33 % women in (sub) top positions. After five years they evaluate the realisation of the target figures. The final goal is to reach gender balance. Ministries set a target for 45 % to 55 % within five years.

In **Israel**, each academic institution that participates in the index (see above), defines its own goals for gender equality and diversity which are approved by the CHE/PBC Steering Committee for Gender Equality. The government has many plans for promoting gender equality and diversity in STEM. These plans include financing training courses for the Arabic, Ethiopian and Religious population.

5.2.4. Objectives to achieve integration of sex, gender and/or intersectional analysis into research and innovation content

Eleven countries formulated objectives to integrate sex and gender analysis into research and innovation content,³⁶ three countries (ES, DE, IE) formulated the objective to integrate intersectional analysis into research and innovation content. Spain is the only country that focused only on intersectional analysis and did not formulate the objective to strengthen sex and gender analysis in the ERA context.

The **Austrian** government is developing guidelines for applications which support integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation content as well as in research-led teaching. These guidelines will be relevant for research funding and the implementation of awareness measures and cross-sectoral cooperation, such as award ceremonies (Gabriele Possanner awards, Diversitas award, Gender Research Day).

The **Belgian** Belspo research programme is pursuing this objective since 2019. Furthermore, the integration of the gender and diversity dimension into research content is implemented in all relevant funding channels of the FWO. Applicants have to indicate how they will deal with gender and diversity in their research and it is part of the evaluation by the expert panels.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy pursues the objective to "reduce inequality stemming from gender insensitive research, development and innovation" by "taking into account the dimension of sex and gender in the content of research, development and innovation as part of support for RDI projects".

³⁶ Germany and Luxembourg did not provide additional information on this objective.

Irish national research funding agencies request applicants to confirm if there is a relevant sex/gender dimension in their research and to provide details of how this is addressed in the research content.

According to the **Spanish** Law 17/202237 that modifies the Law 14/2011 of Science, Technology and Innovation [...] a gender perspective [will be promoted] in all aspects of scientific and technical research, including, where appropriate, intersectionality with other relevant aspects, such as socio-economic status or ethnicity. [...] measures to integrate intersectionality both in the design of gender equality policies in science and innovation and in the content of research and knowledge transfer [will be adopted].

In **Lithuania** it is recommended to integrate gender analysis into scientific projects as a way to implement horizontal priorities.

In **Slovenia**, the objective is addressed by the Scientific Research and Innovation Act and the Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy.

The **Swedish** government formulated instructions for RFOs to aim for integrating gender perspectives in research funding, when this is relevant.

In the **Netherlands**, ZonMw, a RFO in the field of health research, launched a programme on sex and gender in research and innovation, funded by the Ministry of Health.³⁸

In **Israel**, specific grants and scholarships are available to promote women in R&I. There are some grants that are specific for women and that focus on the research of gender dimensions.

5.2.5. Objectives to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment

Fifteen countries formulated objectives to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment.³⁹

The **Austrian** Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research aims at raising awareness and making gender-based violence and sexual harassment visible in higher education and research (funding) institutions, as well as at developing measures to prevent or combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

In **Belgium**, a contact persons network for all authorities is in place and there is commitment from universities to counteract gender-based violence.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy sets an aim to "increase the quality and transparency of HR management at universities and research institutions" through a measure of "taking into account quality and transparency of HR in evaluating research projects by documenting a high quality and transparent institutional solution to HR development and gender equality". An advanced standard in the field of human resources including gender equality (e.g. on issues of sexual harassment, transparent conditions for repeated short-term contracts, work life balance, etc.) will be taken into account in the competition for research funding from public sources. Furthermore, priority 1 of the Action plan for prevention of domestic and gender-based violence aims at the implementation of preventive measures in the field of

³⁷ https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2022-14581

³⁸ <https://www.zonmw.nl/en/get-started-sex-and-gender-research-and-innovation>

³⁹ Luxembourg did not provide additional information on this objective.

domestic and gender-based violence (including sexual harassment and cyber violence and basic knowledge about violence) in educational facilities including higher education institutions.

In **Denmark**, the state, the employers' organisations and the labour unions agreed on a set of initiatives (including policies) that will counteract sexual harassment under the "Tripartite agreement" on Sexual harassment in 2022. This is also having an impact on higher education institutions.

In **Finland**, each higher education institution must prepare the equality and non-equality plan, which focuses also on possible cases of gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

In 2019, **France** adopted a law that makes gender equality plans mandatory for all public institutions. This law mandates measures against gender-based violence, and specifically requires all public employers to set up a dedicated service to support sexual violence victims. In 2021, a dedicated national policy has been adopted by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research, with a 14 million Euro budget over five years. The national executive strategy is framed by a plan, entitled « plan national de lutte contre les violences sexistes et sexuelles dans l'enseignement supérieur et la recherche 2021-2025 », which puts the fight against gender-based violence at the forefront of national politics. This plan aims to collectively take a new step in the fight against gender-based violence, by instilling a change in practices and behaviours at all levels. It consists of 21 measures, structured around four major axes/objectives: (1) Massive and systematic training of the higher education and research community; (2) Strengthening services in universities that are dedicated to supporting victims of violence and discrimination; (3) Communicating at the national level on these issues and (4) Promoting student initiatives.

The **Lithuanian** Labor Code stipulates the obligation for all employers (incl. RPO) to implement measures aimed at preventing all types of harassment. Furthermore, the Lithuanian Universities Rectors Conference approved Guidelines for the Prevention and Investigation of Sexual Harassment.⁴⁰

In **Portugal**, a commission responsible for a strategy to prevent harassment in higher education institutions was recently announced by the government. This commission is formed by representatives of universities and polytechnics, public and private, federations and associations of higher education students, the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality and the Commission for Equality in Work and Employment. The Commission is in charge of elaborating (until the end of 2024) a strategy to prevent and combat harassment in higher education, addressing teaching and research staff, non-teaching staff and students. A Parliament recommendation was issued addressing HEIs to have codes of conduct in place, as well as creating an independent structure to support gender-based violence (GBV) victims and whistleblowers in those institutions. At the FCT level, there is already a code of Conduct in force and a whistleblower channel.

In **Slovakia**, the formal and informal procedures for reporting cases of sexual harassment of the Slovak Academy of Sciences have also influenced the Centre for Scientific and Technical Information in planning training activities aimed at raising awareness of gender-based violence - provided within the framework of the Consultancy Service of the Centre for Scientific and Technical Information (covered by the SK4ERA II. project) to institutions aspiring for funding from the Horizon Europe programme.

In **Slovenia**, the objective is addressed by the Scientific Research and Innovation Act and the Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy. Currently, an amendment of the Higher Education Act is under

⁴⁰ <https://lurk.lt/dokumentai/seksualinio-priekabiavimo-prevencijos-ir-atveju-nagrinejimo-gaires/>

preparation to include a regulation on measures and procedures against violence, harassment, and bullying in HE.

In **Spain**, the law on R&I (2022) requests from all public bodies in the Spanish R&I system to develop GEPs and sexual/sexist harassment protocols with an annual monitoring.

The **Dutch** Minister of Education, Culture and Science published a policy on harassment (social safety, including sexual harassment) in higher education and research in June 2023. In concrete, the minister published an agenda/action plan with the aim of establishing a safe working and learning environment. He set five lines of action. Some attend to the national law on higher education and science, others to the support systems regarding complaints. The most ambitious line of action is the establishment of a national programme that fosters the collaboration between all Dutch higher education institutions on achieving a safe environment within the institutions. The minister made € 4 million a year available for this programme.

Each **Israeli** academic institution is obliged to have a counsel/commissioner for preventing sexual harassment. This is a special position within the academic world. Most women in this position are professors and deal with all cases related to sexual abuse. The institutions that take part in the index (see above) must have someone in this position and have a report each year about all cases.

In **Norway**, universities and university colleges are obliged to deal with gender-based violence and sexual harassment due to the Universities Act.

5.2.6. Objectives to reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation

Thirteen countries state that they are pursuing this goal.⁴¹

In **Austria**, the Federal Ministry on Education, Science and Research organises an annual networking forum on gender and diversity competence for higher education and research institutions.

The **Czech** Gender Equality Strategy uses intersectionality as a cross-cutting principle.

Ireland adopted a Race Equality Implementation Plan 2022-2024 (HEA 2022b) which contains 9 actions. 21 HEIs have signed and endorsed the Anti-Racism Principles⁴². Ireland has a National Access Plan (HEA/Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science 2022) which identifies three main groups who are underrepresented in higher education: students who are socioeconomically disadvantaged; are members of Irish Traveller and Roma communities and have disabilities, including intellectual disabilities. Furthermore, HEIs have a legal obligation, contained in Section 42 of the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act 2014, to have regard to the need to eliminate discrimination, promote equality of opportunity and protect the human rights of public sector staff and service users.

In **France**, the inter-ministerial plans are implemented to tackle inequalities related to racial/ethnic origin and sexual orientation/gender identity. These plans aim at measuring discriminations and ensuring

⁴¹ Spain, Luxembourg and Finland do not provide additional information regarding the objective.

⁴² <https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2022/03/Anti-Racism-Principles-for-Irish-Higher-Education-Institutions.pdf>

effective access to rights.⁴³ Regarding disability, just like private employers, the French public administration is required to employ disabled workers, accounting for at least 6 % of the total number of salaried employees.

In **Lithuania**, gender equality and inclusiveness are integrated into all competitive financial instruments as a compulsory cross-cutting priority.

In **Portugal**, a non-discrimination and equal access principle is embedded in all programmes and regulations of the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT). “No candidate can be deprived from any right, or exempt from any duty, in reason of ascendancy, age, sex, sexual orientation, marital state, family situation, economic situation”. Furthermore, FCT’s evaluation panels are composed in a way that all scientific areas are covered, and the criteria gender balance, geographical and institutional are met. Due these measures, mainly in statutes and regulations, there are no specific targets or objectives formulated.

In **Slovakia**, related objectives are included in the National Strategy for Gender Equality and in antidiscrimination legislation.

In **Sweden**, the objective is pursued by the Discrimination Act since 2010.

In the **Netherlands**, a National Action Plan for Greater Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education and Research is in place.⁴⁴ The plan sets five objectives for 2025: (1) to embed diversity more effectively in existing instruments, (2) to monitor diversity more widely in education and research, including social safety and inclusion, (3) to establish an award system to provide frameworks and set the direction for policy and funding, ensuring that they are diverse and inclusive, (4) to bring together and support institutional diversity plans, enabling more cooperation and (5) to establish a national centre of excellence for diversity and inclusion. This centre of excellence will develop, bring together and share knowledge and expertise.

In **Israel**, these potential sources of bias are addressed by specific plans. For example, special plans for Bedouin in the South, plans for Ethiopian students and students who are the first in their family to study are in place. There are also special plans for those with disability.

In **Norway**, these dimensions are mentioned in the Act relating to equality and a prohibition against discrimination (Equality and Anti-Discrimination Act⁴⁵).

5.3. Gender equality measures

Apart from Slovakia all countries are implementing or planning to implement at least one gender equality measure at national or regional level.⁴⁶ 16 countries mention that they are active regarding the

⁴³ Plan national pour l'égalité, contre la haine et les discriminations anti LGBT+ (2023-2026) (<https://www.egalite-femmes-hommes.gouv.fr/plan-national-pour-legalite-contre-la-haine-et-les-discriminations-anti-lgbt-2023-2026>) and Plan national de lutte contre le racisme, l'antisémitisme et les discriminations liées à l'origine (2023-2026) (<https://www.egalite-femmes-hommes.gouv.fr/engagements-du-gouvernement-face-au-racisme-et-lantisemitisme>).

⁴⁴ <https://www.dihoo.eu/topics/national-action-plan>

⁴⁵ <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NLE/lov/2017-06-16-51?q=equality>

⁴⁶ Please note that the information provided on planned or implemented measures relates to the time of the survey, which was conducted in April/May 2024. It is possible that measures planned at that time may have already been implemented.

achievement of fair, open, inclusive and gender equality career paths. An equal number of countries supports institutional and structural change – in most cases by supporting the uptake of GEPs at institutional level. Similarly, 16 countries pursue measures to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment. 15 countries not only pursue gender equality but consider at least one additional dimension causing structural inequalities in their policies. In 13 countries specific measures aim at supporting the integration of sex, gender and/or intersectional analysis in research content. 12 countries have or plan measures to achieve gender balance and/or diversity in decision making.

Table 5: Countries with gender equality measures implemented or planned at national level

Measures	Implemented	Planned	Neither nor	Description provided
... achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths	10	6	3	2
... achieve systemic institutional and structural change, i.e. supporting the uptake of (inclusive) gender equality plans	14	2	3	12
... achieve gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making	10	2	7	0
... achieve integration of sex, gender and/or intersectional analysis into research and innovation content	8	5	6	7
... counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment	10	6	3	10
... reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation	11	4	4	3

Source: GENDERACTIONplus survey 2024.

Although almost all countries participating in the survey report that they are taking measures, only a few provide further information (see Table 11 in Annex). More detailed information on specific implemented or planned policies or measures is available for 14 countries, some of which was provided by respondents and some of which was obtained through supplementary desk research. This information is presented in the form of factsheets in the annex (including a reference to the source). Most factsheets are available for France (16), followed by the Czech Republic and Ireland (6 each), Austria (4), Germany (3), Denmark and Spain (2 each). For the other countries (Finland, Israel, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland and Portugal), there is one factsheet available. In total, information for 46 policies or measures is available.

The measures described in the factsheets have different focuses, scopes and target groups, and they differ considerably in terms of the resources used. They are therefore difficult to compare, and the number of measures does not appear to be very meaningful. However, they do show which gender equality policy objectives are being addressed by specific measures and where there are gaps.

Twelve of these policies or measures can be classified as transversal, as they do not address a specific issue but either provide the legal basis for measures addressing several equality issues (e.g. the Danish Gender Equality Act) or aim to provide empirical evidence to analyse policy implementation (e.g. the annual statistical report on the position of women in research in Czech research).

Six countries each mention measures to support structural change in science and research and to mainstream sex/gender/intersectional analyses. Three countries mention measures to combat gender-based violence, and two address career paths with specific measures. Only one country (Ireland) explicitly describes measures that address inequalities beyond gender. To be concrete, Ireland developed a policy with specific measures on race equality. Particularly noteworthy is the focus in France on gender-based violence: 8 measures address this issue.

It is evident that the issues of career paths, gender-based violence and inequalities beyond gender are only addressed in exceptional cases. There is a distinct absence of specific measures taken to support gender balance in decision-making bodies in any country. This demonstrates a clear discrepancy between the stated political objectives and the areas addressed by planned or implemented measures.

Figure 7: Topics addressed by policies or measures (implemented or planned)

Source: GENDERACTIONplus survey 2024 (factsheets).

22 of the measures described were identified by respondents as exemplifying good practices for a variety of reasons. While measures may not be directly transferable to other contexts, an exchange of

insights regarding the expectations that underpin their design and experiences with their implementation could prove beneficial for other countries.

5.4. Gender (equality) monitoring

Respondents have been asked if a regular and systematic collection of information regarding gender equality takes place at national or regional level which complements She Figures. The respondents were presented with a list of potential topics for inclusion in such a monitoring.

In most countries, data regarding the representation of women in decision-making in HEIs is regularly collected. Similarly, information on the participation of women in R&I sectors is also available. Additionally, data on the involvement of women in decision-making bodies in R&I outside of HEIs is accessible in 11 countries. In seven countries, the monitoring includes information on the proportion of RPOs with a GEP in place. However, only in five countries is it known how many RFOs have adopted a GEP. In contrast, information on whether the GEP is also implemented and whether structures for the implementation of equality measures have been created at the institutional level is much less common.

Furthermore, there is a notable lack of information concerning strategies for addressing gender-based violence as well as the integration of a gender dimension in R&I content, in curricula (study courses in gender studies) and professorships in gender studies. Only in three or four countries are this information available. Only two countries systematically collect information regarding the gender competence of teaching staff in HEIs and no country monitoring contains information about intersectional approaches in R&I content.

It is evident that there is a convergence between the political objective and existing empirical evidence in instances where women's participation in decision-making, particularly within HEIs, is concerned. In this area, the achievement of the political objective can be discussed referring to empirical evidence. Conversely, 15 countries have established a political objective to facilitate structural change. Nevertheless, data is currently accessible for only six countries regarding the number of RPOs and for five countries regarding the number of RFOs with a GEP. Information concerning the implementation of GEPs is seldom available. The discrepancy is even more evident with regard to combating gender-based violence and integrating a sex/gender/intersectional perspective into the content of research and teaching.

Figure 8: Topics covered by a national monitoring

Source: GENDERACTIONplus survey 2024.

In most cases, the national statistics authorities are involved in the collection of this information (12 countries). In addition, specific institutions are involved in the collection of information in 12 countries, including quality assurance agencies and policy actors (e.g., Higher Education Authorities, Science Council). Ministries are involved in seven countries, while RFOs are involved in another seven countries.

6. Summary and conclusions

Gender equality has been one of ERA's priorities for more than a decade. In 2021, most Member States and Associated Countries renewed and reinforced their commitment to gender equality by endorsing the **Ljubljana Declaration**. With the Ljubljana Declaration, the main stakeholders in R&I (EC, MS/AC) agreed on the directions of further development: to address gender-based violence, to move from a gender oriented to an intersectional approach to gender equality and to focus on GEPs as the most significant instrument to achieve sustainable progress towards gender equality in R&I. The Ljubljana Declaration referred to the **Pact for Research and Innovation** in Europe adopted by the Council of the European Union in 2021. The Council also established the ERA Policy Agenda which sets out the ERA actions to be implemented. ERA Action 5 focuses on gender quality and inclusiveness. Not all Member States that endorsed the Ljubljana Declaration also expressed a commitment to ERA Action 5. In total 22 Member States and three other countries committed themselves to ERA Action 5: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Georgia (observer), Ireland, Israel (AC), Italy, Lithuania, Luxemburg, the Netherlands, Norway (AC), Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.

This commitment to ERA Action 5 was expressed by a written statement from MS/AC. Compared to the previous ERA period (2015-2020), there is now a more detailed description provided by the European Commission of what is expected from Member States which are committed to pursuing gender equality and inclusiveness. However, as there is no requirement to formulate a national action plan as in the previous ERA period, there is only limited information available regarding MS/AC priorities, objectives and planned or implemented measures.

To gather comprehensive data on strategies, objectives and measures related to gender equality in the ERA, a survey was conducted among members of the ERA Forum Subgroup on Gender and Inclusiveness. Nineteen countries participated in the survey (17 Member States and 2 associated countries), so the situation of countries who committed themselves to ERA Action 5 is well covered. However, it should be noted that the results are not representative of all EU Member States. With 12 responses the survey reflects the situation of the 'old' Member States (former EU 15) quite well, but not that of the widening countries (5 responses).

Of the countries that have committed to ERA Action 5, just over half have formulated an ERA action plan or a gender equality strategy that refers to ERA. However, even in the absence of a strategic document, the majority of countries represented in the survey have formulated gender equality policy objectives based on ERA action 5. These objectives, however, lack specific, measurable and time-bound objectives (SMART) and instead represent a **commitment to address specific challenges without the formulation of concrete targets**.

Even though a large number of objectives have been formulated and the topics from ERA Action 5 have been adopted in principle, this is not mirrored in the measures that are planned or implemented in each of these areas. Fourteen countries provide information on at least one measure. Six countries are implementing measures to support structural change in HEIs and RPOs, and measures to strengthen sex/gender-analysis or intersectional research. Only a few countries are implementing measures to promote inclusive career paths, to combat gender-based violence, to promote gender balance in decision-making or to address inequalities beyond gender.

It should be noted that **discrepancies between the formulated goals and their implementation** are not solely evident in these measures. This also applies to monitoring. Regarding the areas addressed by the targets, there is only **very limited information available**.

One might now inquire as to whether the discrepancy between stated objectives and actual activities represents a significant issue, as the stated goals have been adopted in principle, and activities have also been implemented in a number of countries. Considering the GENDERACTIONplus approach to policymaking (see chapter 4), the answer is yes. **It is not prudent to focus on measures in isolation, as activity without a clearly defined goal is unlikely to achieve the desired outcome. This approach carries the risk of inefficient use of resources and may result in a lack of acceptance or even resistance to the objective.**

The existing activities, many of which are regarded as good practice by respondents, could serve as a starting point for mutual learning and exchange between countries, facilitating the development of measures or the enhancement of existing approaches. It is essential to not only focus on the rationale behind the design of a measure but also to examine the experiences gained from its implementation, particularly regarding obstacles or resistance encountered.

A more significant issue, however, is the **absence of effective monitoring** of the implementation of ERA Action 5, which constrains the potential for a comprehensive European gender equality policy discourse. This refers not only to the lack of information regarding relevant outcome indicators (such as the number of institutions which adopted a gender equality plan), but also the lack of information on the national or regional gender equality policy strategy including its priorities, objectives and measures. **Even if a lot of information on the status quo of gender equality in science and research is available for individual countries (e.g., via the SHE Figures), this offers little insight into the implementation of ERA Action 5.**

Given the current data set, it is not feasible to draw comparisons between the status of gender equality policies across Member States and Associated Countries, nor to ascertain whether these policies have evolved in a particular direction. Furthermore, an analysis of the consistency and coherence of gender equality policy strategies is not feasible.

The absence of a unified and coherent gender equality policy in the ERA also results in **inefficiencies in the policymaking process**. It is evident that several countries are developing measures in parallel, which results in a lack of coordination and the potential of gender equality policy is lost. This also allows stakeholders to understand concepts differently which contradicts the assumption of policy-makers at European and national level that there is a coherent and consistent understanding of the concepts used in European documents.⁴⁷ Furthermore, the lack of exchange when (re)designing measures also means that existing synergies may not be used and mistakes that have already been made are repeated in other contexts.

The combination of a political steering mechanism in ERA, which relies on voluntary action in the area of gender equality and inclusiveness, with a lack of reporting or monitoring on the implementation of gender equality policy at the national level, means that the voluntary commitment is not regarded as a binding obligation or a matter of accountability.

⁴⁷ However, the GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking reports show that concepts are interpreted differently and policies or measures referring to the same concepts are comparable only to a limited extent.

To maintain and further develop the status quo of gender equality engagement in ERA, it is essential to **complement the voluntary character of political commitment with robust monitoring and an intensified gender equality policy discourse**. To achieve this, the following is proposed:

- In order to fully leverage the potential of monitoring for steering policy, it is important in the future to not only request that countries make a commitment to an ERA action on a voluntary basis, but also to ensure that this is translated into a concrete national action plan (binding self-commitment with the correspondent resources and responsibilities).
- To intensify the European discourse on inclusive gender equality by involving high-level policy-makers (e.g. ERAC members).
- To provide a platform for mutual learning and exchange already in the phase of policy development. This would support countries with little experience in particular and provide a possibility to reflect on already implemented measures for more experienced countries.
- To systematically collect information on the implementation of national and/or regional gender equality policies from the start of the implementation period and integrate this information in existing monitoring systems such as the ERA Monitoring Mechanism (ERA Scoreboard, ERA Dashboard) and She Figures.
- To use the results of the monitoring for awareness raising activities (e.g. public presentation of the monitoring at European and national level) and for showcasing identified good practices.

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ANNEX 1 – TABLES

Table 6: She Figures indicators focusing on women's representation (2021)

	Grade A	Heads of HEIs	% women doctoral graduates	% women researchers
EU27	26,18	23,60	48,10	32,80
BE	20,29	37,00	43,90	34,80
BG	39,70	25,50	53,10	47,40
CZ	n.d.	17,20	43,70	26,60
DK	22,55	33,30	49,00	35,80
DE	20,47	23,20	45,20	27,90
EE	n.d.	20,00	48,40	42,20
IE	25,63	18,20	51,00	36,30
EL	22,29	16,00	47,40	37,80
ES	23,90	18,00	52,60	40,50
FR	27,65	12,10	43,90	28,30
HR	43,02	26,50	53,90	48,40
IT	23,74	25,40	50,50	34,30
CY	13,30	9,10	49,20	38,10
LV	44,65	44,20	54,50	52,20
LT	40,40	39,00	57,90	49,50
LU	17,67	0,00	35,60	28,10
HU	21,64	17,20	46,20	30,50
MT	43,75	29,30	50,90	30,90
NL	22,25	22,70	48,10	26,40
AT	25,09	26,80	44,00	30,10
PL	25,22	19,60	56,30	38,10
PT	27,15	27,20	52,90	43,30
RO	50,78	11,10	53,20	46,70
SI	32,95	32,70	54,00	32,30
SK	27,23	22,90	49,20	41,20
FI	30,32	20,50	52,00	33,20
SE	28,22	41,70	47,90	32,60
UK	26,41	24,20	46,60	38,80
IS	26,32	40,00	59,00	46,40
NO	30,91	25,80	50,40	38,10
CH	24,08	24,40	44,80	34,90
TR	30,46	28,00	46,90	37,00
BA	46,56	25,50	46,70	44,30
IL	19,45	21,60	53,10	n.d.

Note: Grade A = Proportion (%) of women among academic staff Grade A, 2018 (p. 184); Heads of HEIs = Proportion (%) of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector, 2019 (p. 200); % women doctoral graduates = Proportion (%) of women among doctoral graduates, 2018 (p. 27); % women researchers = Proportion (%) of women among researchers, 2018 (p. 97)
Source: EC (2021c)

Table 7: She Figures indicators focusing career prospects (GCI) and gender dimension in R&I content (2021)

	GCI 2018	GDRIC 2015-2019	%H2020 GD	% H2020 IA
EU27	1,58	1,80	1,65	0,19
BE	1,73	1,76	1,25	0,10
BG	1,21	1,79	1,92	0,21
CZ	n.d.	1,76	1,40	0,00
DK	1,66	2,42	1,15	0,17
DE	1,33	1,46	1,19	0,09
EE	n.d.	2,44	2,06	0,00
IE	2,16	1,90	2,11	0,29
EL	1,41	2,05	1,26	0,04
ES	1,90	2,17	1,42	0,11
FR	1,47	1,30	1,32	0,08
HR	1,23	3,03	0,70	0,00
IT	1,71	1,48	1,47	0,17
CY	2,60	2,46	1,64	0,00
LV	1,42	1,18	0,31	0,00
LT	1,42	2,45	1,52	0,00
LU	1,68	1,60	0,78	0,00
HU	1,94	1,89	1,56	0,00
MT	0,87	2,96	2,96	0,00
NL	1,71	2,09	1,46	0,16
AT	1,55	1,87	1,58	0,16
PL	1,78	2,03	1,81	0,07
PT	1,71	1,93	1,93	0,21
RO	1,03	1,17	1,24	0,00
SI	1,39	1,73	2,68	0,26
SK	1,74	1,95	1,95	0,00
FI	1,56	2,73	1,52	0,17
SE	1,59	3,20	1,83	0,22
UK	1,64	1,94	1,74	0,22
IS	1,41	4,01	1,94	0,00
NO	1,50	2,96	1,57	0,06
CH	1,57	1,80	1,27	0,03
TR	1,24	3,71	2,20	0,47
BA	1,00	4,30	5,36	0,00
IL	2,33	2,17	1,56	0,21

Note: GCI= Glass Ceiling Index, 2015-2018 (p. 194); GDRIC = Percentage of a country's publications with a gender dimension in their research and innovation content, 2015-2019 (p. 264); %H2020 GD = Proportion (%) of Horizon 2020 projects integrating a gender dimension (p. 269); %H2020 IA = Proportion (%) of Horizon 2020 projects integrating an intersectionality approach (p. 270)
Source: EC (2021c)

Table 8: Share of RPOs with GEPs

	GEPs
EU28	55,9
BE	83,3
BG	14,3
CZ	14,3
DK	50,0
DE	92,9
EE	0,0
IE	60,0
EL	50,0
ES	75,0
FR	81,8
HR	20,0
IT	38,9
CY	50,0
LV	0,0
LT	0,0
LU	n.d.
HU	38,5
MT	0,0
NL	43,5
AT	74,3
PL	22,2
PT	25,0
RO	20,0
SI	22,2
SK	12,5
FI	78,9
SE	95,2
UK	91,3

Source: EC (2019d: 108)

Table 9: Gender Equality Index (2023)

	EIGE GEI
EU27	70,2
BE	76,0
BG	65,1
CZ	59,7
DK	77,8
DE	70,8
EE	60,2
IE	73,0
EL	58,0
ES	76,4
FR	75,7
HR	60,7
IT	68,2
CY	60,7
LV	61,5
LT	64,1
LU	74,7
HU	57,3
MT	67,8
NL	77,9
AT	71,2
PL	61,9
PT	67,4
RO	56,1
SI	69,4
SK	59,2
FI	74,4
SE	82,2

Source: EIGE (2023)

Table 10: Summary Innovation Index (SII), normalised scores

	SII
EU27	110,0
BE	136,0
BG	50,6
CZ	98,7
DK	149,3
DE	122,8
EE	115,3
IE	124,5
EL	85,3
ES	98,9
FR	114,4
HR	76,6
IT	98,6
CY	116,9
LV	59,0
LT	92,0
LU	123,3
HU	77,6
MT	96,8
NL	138,3
AT	127,9
PL	72,5
PT	91,8
RO	37,4
SI	100,1
SK	71,6
FI	140,6
SE	146,2
UK	126,3
IS	110,6
NO	128,7
CH	152,2
TR	56,9
BA	36,4
IL	n.d.

Source: EC (2024: 140)

Table 11: Commitment to ERA Action 5, gender equality issues and measures implemented or planned by country

ERA Action 5 commitment	commitment to GE							measures implemented/planned					
	careers	structural change	diversity in decision making	sex/gender/intersect. analysis	gender based violence	inequalities beyond gender	careers	structural change	diversity in decision making	sex/gender/intersect. analysis	gender based violence	inequalities beyond gender	
BE	x	x	x	x	x	x	0	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
BG	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
CZ	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	x	0	x	(x)	(x)
DK	x	x	x	x	0	x	0	(x)	(x)	(x)	x	(x)	(x)
DE	x	x	x	x	x	0	0	(x)	x	(x)	x	(x)	(x)
EE	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
IE	x	x	x	x	x	0	x	(x)	x	(x)	x	(x)	x
ES	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	0	0	x	x	(x)
FR	x	x	x	x	0	x	x	(x)	x	0	0	x	(x)
HR	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
IT	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
CY	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
LV	x	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda	nda
LT	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
LU	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
NL	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
AT	x	x	x	0	x	x	x	0	x	0	x	x	0
PL	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	x	0	0	0	0
PT	x	x	0	x	0	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	0	(x)	(x)
SI	x	0	0	x	x	x	nda	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
SK	x	0	0	0	0	x	x	0	0	0	0	0	0
FI	x	x	x	nda	0	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
SE	x	x	x	x	x	0	x	(x)	0	0	0	0	0
NO	x	x	x	0	0	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)
IL	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)

(x) measures implemented or planned but not information on the measures available; no information available for: EL, HU, MT, RO, UK, IS, CH, TR, BA

Source: GENDERACTIONplus survey 2024.

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ANNEX 2 – QUESTIONNAIRE

**GENDER
ACTION+**

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101058093.

Survey on implementation of ERA Action 5 at national or regional level

1 Please indicate the national/regional authority you represent.

Country: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Authority: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

2 Did your country formulate a national or regional ERA action plan for the period 2022-2024?

Yes

No

Don't Know

If yes, please provide a link to the document or attach the document.

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

3 Did your country formulate a national and/or regional policy on gender equality focusing on R&I and/or higher education institutions which refers to ERA? Please select all appropriate options.

Yes, national policy

Yes, regional policy

No

If yes, please provide a link to the document or attach the document.

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Gender Equality Objectives

Hint: In the following, when we ask about objectives, we mean whether the desired outcome of a policy is formulated, e.g. to support RPOs in ... or to increase the proportion of research projects that meet certain criteria.

4 Are specific objectives formulated to achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths for your country/region? If yes, please give details.

Yes [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

No

5 Are specific objectives formulated to achieve systemic institutional and structural change, i.e. supporting the uptake of (inclusive) gender equality plans for your country/region? If yes, please give details.

Yes [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

No

6 Are specific objectives formulated to ensure gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making for your country/region? If yes, please give details.

Yes [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

No

7 Are specific objectives formulated to foster the integration of sex, gender and intersectional analysis into research and innovation content for your country/region? If yes, please give details. Please select all appropriate options.

Yes, integration of sex and gender analysis [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Yes, integration of intersectional analysis

No

2

8 Are specific objectives formulated to counteract **gender-based violence including sexual harassment** in R&I and/or higher education institutions for your country/region? If yes, please give details.

Yes

Click or tap here to enter text.

No

9 Are specific objectives formulated to **reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation** for your country/region? If yes, please give details for the criteria applicable.

Yes

Click or tap here to enter text.

No

Gender Equality Measures planned and implemented

10 Are measures implemented (2023) or planned (2024) which focus on the following objectives? If yes, please describe each measures using the attached factsheet or provide us with a link to further information.

	Implemented	Planned	Link
to achieve fair, open, inclusive and gender equal career paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.
to achieve systemic institutional and structural change, i.e. supporting the uptake of (inclusive) gender equality plans	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.
to ensure gender balance and/or increase diversity in decision making	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.
to foster the integration of sex, gender and intersectional analysis into research and innovation content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.
to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.
to reduce inequalities regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Click or tap here to enter text.

11 Does a regular and systematic collection of information (monitoring) – which complements She Figures – on the following topics exist in your country/region. Please select all appropriate options.

- Women's representation by R&I sector
- Women's representation in decision making in higher education institutions
- Women's representation in decision making in R&I
- Study courses in gender studies
- Professorships in gender studies
- Gender competence of teaching staff in higher education institutions
- Gender dimension in research and innovation content
- Intersectional approaches in research and innovation content
- Prevalence of gender-based violence including sexual harassment
- Share of RPOs with a GEP in place
- Share of RPOs with established structures for gender equality
- Share of RPOs which implement gender equality measures
- Share of RFOs with a GEP in place
- Share of RFOs with established structures for gender equality
- Share of RFOs which implement gender equality measures
- Information on the implementation of national policies (e.g. number of participants, budget spent)
- Other, please specify: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

5

12 Which of the following institutions/actors are systematically collecting information on the topics mentioned in question 11? Please select all appropriate options.

- National statistics office
- Federal Ministries (e.g. of Education, Science, Research, Innovation)
- Other national or regional authorities, e.g.
- RFO(s)

13 Have the questions above missed any important issues relating to the implementation of ERA Action 5? If yes, please let us know.

Thank you for your cooperation!

ANNEX 3 – FACTSHEETS

Austria

Gender Equality Plan Workshops (AT)

Name of the measure	Development and implementation of formats to support the (further) development of equality plans based on the process steps formulated in the "Guidelines for the development of equality plans", as well as quality standards for higher education and research (funding) institutions and communication of examples of good practice
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	Application-oriented formats for target group-specific further training and for the exchange between relevant actors in higher education and research (funding) institutions, with regard to the process steps in the development of gender equality plans.
Target group	Gender Experts in HEIs, RPOs, RFOs
Approach/content	The Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research and the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology are jointly organising three online training courses on the (further) development of gender equality plans at Austrian higher education and research (funding) institutions. The training courses are based on the guidelines for the development of equality plans published by the BMBWF and BMK as well as the relevant documents published by the European Commission. This support format is a measure within the framework of the National Action Plan for the European Research Area (ERA-NAP) 2022-2025 and is targeted at gender equality stakeholders at Austrian universities and research (funding) institutions. Participants will be familiarised with a typical process for developing a gender equality plan, which will be illustrated by concrete examples of promising practice. There will also be an opportunity to raise specific questions and discuss the transferability of the good practice examples.
Results	Two workshops have already been held. Both events had over 100 participants. The participants see Horizon Europe's requirement that applicant organisations must present a GEP as a push factor for equality policies. However, they also emphasised the need for support. Furthermore, it became clear that the exchange on the conception of GEPs and experiences with specific initiatives is important and helpful, whereby the exchange of experiences with regard to good practices as well as failed measures is encouraged. The participants

	emphasised that cross-institutional and cross-sectoral measures are important and would presumably also be efficient in terms of the use of resources.
Resources (per year)	€ 12.000
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The programme not only provides input and promising practices, but also tries to connect the different sectors (universities, non-university research and entrepreneurial research) through the possibility of exchange. In this way, despite many different framework conditions, similarities can also be discussed. However, the programme also faces a challenge, as the differences between the sectors - and possibly also the high number of participants and the online format - make an open discussion difficult in some cases
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Gender Equality Plan Supporting Structure (AT)

Name of the measure	Development of a concept for the implementation of appropriate coordination structures for the (further) development, implementation and monitoring of gender equality plans at national level
Introduced in	Not yet introduced, planned for 2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	The coordination structure is intended to create cross-sector governance between the three ministries involved in research (BMBWF, BMK, BMAW) in order to promote the development and implementation of quality-assured equality plans at higher education and research (funding) institutions at national level.
Target group	HEIs, RPOs, RFOs
Approach/content	The following tasks are part of this cross-sectoral governance: The gender equality plans developed by the higher education and research institutions must be evaluated/monitored externally. In addition to the content-related quality check regarding the compliance with formal and content-related requirements, feedback and exchange with the institutions must also be provided in order to promote the further development of the equality plan. Higher education and research (funding) institutions must be supported in the (further) development of their equality plans, especially in the coming years.
Results	---
Resources (per year)	Not yet decided
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Gender Research Day and Networking Forum (AT)

Name of the measure	Cross sectoral Cooperation: Gender Research Day and annual networking forum on gender and diversity competence for higher education and research institutions
Introduced in	2021/2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The Gender Research Day should create awareness and visibility for the sex, gender and intersectional analyses into research and innovation content. The networking forum aims to further strengthen networking between the various stakeholders in the organisations
Target group	Higher Education and Research (Funding) Institutions
Approach/content	Gender Research Day: Each two years, higher education and research institutions are invited to present contributions on gender research. On the one hand, this is intended to highlight the societal and scientific relevance of this research approach in education, teaching and research content. On the other hand, the various contributions of gender research to the promotion of excellence are to be highlighted and made visible in this way: BMBWF Tag der Geschlechterforschung - TaskCards. Furthermore awarding ceremonies are part of the gender research day. The Networking Format is seen as an important driver for the intended gender and diversity-oriented cultural change (Fix the institutions) and as a link for current diversity-oriented equality topics between the BMBWF and the institutions, in addition to the development and broadening of expertise the building of a community of practice is also aimed: https://bmbwf.taskcards.app/#/board/3dd3cc6f-e903-4b13-9fc8-48512b9040b0/view?token=eaaa4a52-91c5-45fb-99ce-0ebe7dfb886e .
Results	Results and further information of the measures are available in the links provided above.
Resources (per year)	€ 130.000 (Gender research Day € 70.000; Network meeting € 60.000)
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://bmbwf.taskcards.app/#/board/3dd3cc6f-e903-4b13-9fc8-48512b9040b0/view?token=eaaa4a52-91c5-45fb-99ce-0ebe7dfb886e

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Gender-based Violence Survey (AT)

Name of the measure	Survey on the status quo of existing legal provisions, contact points and information centres and measures regarding gender based violence
Introduced in	Not yet introduced, planned for 2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	The aim of the survey is to obtain a comprehensive overview of the existing legal framework, support structures and preventive measures to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment at Austrian higher education and research institutions. The data collected will then serve as a basis for the development of more effective strategies and measures to combat gender-based violence at these institutions and create a safer environment for all members of the higher education and research community.
Target group	HEIs, RPOs
Approach/content	Data collection: Collection of existing legal provisions, contact and support centres and existing measures to prevent and combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment at Austrian higher education and research institutions. Analysis and evaluation: Analysing the collected data, identifying trends, strengths and weaknesses in the existing systems and measures and providing recommendations for possible improvements. Preparation of a detailed report: Collection of all findings, results and recommendations in a report
Results	---
Resources (per year)	Not yet decided
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Too early to answer this question
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

The Czech Republic

Annual statistical report on the position of women in Czech research: She Figures (CZ)

Name of the measure	Annual statistical report on the position of women in Czech research: She Figures the Czech Republic
Introduced in	2008
Description of the measure	
Objective	Provide annual statistical reports on the proportion of women in Czech research
Target group	Policy-makers and civil servants in public administration bodies, research funding organisations, research performing organisations, academic community and general public
Approach/content	The report brings annual statistical data on the proportions of women from ISCED 5 to Grade A full professors, across disciplinary fields and research sectors. It presents the proportions of women in leadership positions in Czech research and a comparison with EU statistics. The Annexes present timelines.
Results	The representation of women in research in the Czech Republic has not increased in the long term, despite the fact that there is an overall increase in the number of people engaged in research activities. The highest representation of women among researchers is in medical and agricultural sciences, while the lowest is in engineering and natural sciences. In European comparison, the Czech Republic has the second lowest proportion of women researchers among all EU Member States. There are more women than men studying at universities, and their representation decreases as the level of education increases. Women tend to enter research careers less after completing their doctoral studies. In 2021, only 18 845 women (27.1 %) were researchers. The representation of women as associate professors and professors in 2021 was 22.9 % and 11.8 % respectively. Based on the current growth rate, parity among associate professors will be reached in 2170 and among professors in 2329. Men predominate in senior R&D positions. Women are under-represented in decision-making, strategic, advisory and control bodies.
Resources (per year)	Approx. 0,3 FTE per year
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	Yes

Recommendation as good practice	Yes
Website	https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/vystupy/2023/M4/Postaveni_zen_v_ceske_vede_2021_eng.pdf https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/vystupy/2024/M4/Postaveni_zen_v_ceske_vede_2022_EN.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Strategic Intelligence for Research and Innovation (CZ)

Name of the measure	Project "Strategic Intelligence for Research and Innovation"
Introduced in	2021
Description of the measure	
Objective	The purpose of the project of shared activities titled "Strategic Intelligence for Research and Innovation" is to provide analytical capacity and data-driven strategic information (i.e. strategic intelligence services) to public administrations and research organisations for the implementation of research, development and innovation (R&D&I) policy in several areas including the development of human resources and capacities for research and innovation, and gender issues and the conditions for women in science. The Centre for Gender and Science is responsible for the implementation of Module 4 - Gender and Science. The project is currently implemented in the period of 2021 to 2024. A follow-up project covering the period 2025 to 2030 is under preparation.
Target group	The main users of the project results are bodies of the public administration, to which strategic intelligence services (analyses and studies) for research and innovation policy are provided, and research organisations and educational institutions, to which analytical support for research activities will be provided.
Approach/content	The project focuses on analytical work which is based on the needs of the Ministry of Youth, Sports and Education and the Office of the Government as primary recipients of the analytical services requested.
Results	In 2023 there were 6 analyses prepared and 1 prevalence study launched within the framework of the project on topics such as adoption and implementation of gender equality plans, measures to address gender-based violence in higher education, adoption and implementation of an impact assessment methodology, mapping of factors influencing interest in ERC grants and others. All results available at: https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/#vystupy .
Resources (per year)	Approx. € 300.000 for the entire duration of the project for Module 4 Gender and Science.
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. With this project, funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, provides multi-annual funding for the creation of strategic intelligence including gender equality in R&I which allows to monitor the implementation of policy goals and commitments such as GEPs, actions to combat gender-based violence. The innovation nature also lies in the fact that the analyses and studies to be performed are approved on an annual basis for the next year,

	which makes it possible to propose new analyses as the needs arise and thus react to policy developments and emerging needs.
Website	https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/#projekt (in Czech only)

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Czech RFO CoP focusing on gender aspects of research funding (CZ)

Name of the measure	Czech RFO CoP focusing on gender aspects of research funding
Introduced in	2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	The aim is to organise meetings for Czech research funders on gender aspects of research funding (e.g. gender dimension in research content, inclusive research careers, bias in the evaluation of proposals, strategies to eliminate gender-based violence, etc.) to build capacities, disseminate the GENDERACTIONplus project's outputs, share good practices and coordinate approaches in the Czech research ecosystem and the ERA.
Target group	Czech research funders and national authorities with budget for research and innovation funding
Approach/content	The Institute of Sociology organises the events with the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (another participant of the GENDERACTIONplus project) and creates the content of these events. GENDERACTIONplus outputs and recommendations are utilised. At least two events per year are foreseen.
Results	One meeting organised (04/2024) with the representatives of eight research funding organisations and ministries
Resources (per year)	0,6 PM / year (will depend on the number of meetings)
Innovative elements	None. The measure uses a proven design. Its contribution lies in connecting organisations less experienced in promoting gender equality in research with more advanced organisations and discussing existing good practice.
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. While the format itself is not new, connecting research funders with varying degrees of experience in promoting gender equality in research, their joint discussion of the concrete design of specific measures and cooperation in their implementation may be seen as a powerful instrument for change in the national research ecosystem, as well as of coordination of actions in the ERA.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

CZERA (CZ)

Name of the measure	The project of shared activities entitled "Deepening the integration of the research and innovation ecosystem of the Czech Republic into the European Research Area and support for intensive international cooperation of research organisations and enterprises of the Czech Republic in research, development and innovation" (hereinafter referred to as "CZERA") with module 2 dedicated to gender equality and gender mainstreaming implemented by the Centre for Gender and Science at the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, covering the entire period of Horizon Europe from 2021 to 2027.
Introduced in	2021
Description of the measure	
Objective	The project focuses on the provision of a comprehensive portfolio of support services necessary for intensive involvement of research and innovation stakeholders of the Czech Republic in the European Research Area. The Centre for Gender and Science is responsible supporting Czech research organisations and teams in relation to international cooperation in the new European research support programme Horizon Europe and the successful fulfilment of Czech, European and international commitments in the field of gender equality in science.
Target group	Universities and research institutions, National authorities, European Commission
Approach/content	The activities in Module 2 focus on 1. Providing expert support to RPOs in relation to gender equality requirements in Horizon Europe with a specific focus on gender equality plans including consultations, training, workshops and other direct support to Czech research organisations, 2. Providing expert support in relation to national policy development through national advisory bodies, 3. Providing expert support in relation to the implementation of EU commitments of the Czech Republic and specifically the implementation of the ERA Action 5, including the execution of the MS co-chairing by Marcela Linkova of the ERA Forum subgroup on inclusive gender equality. The project also conducts outreach activities and organises public events and awareness raising activities including the campaign One Size Doesn't Fit All to raise awareness among expert and general public about the gender dimension in research and innovation.
Results	Information on trainings and learning materials are available on the Centre's website. All results available at: https://genderaveda.cz/plany-genderoverovnosti/
Resources (per year)	Approx. € 1,423.000 for the entire project period

Innovative elements	The project activities for which the Centre is responsible are very complex and include various stakeholders including higher education institutions, research institutions, state bodies, individual change-agents on the level of institutions as well as the general public. The project provides funding for free training materials provided to institutions, expert policy advice and awareness-raising activities
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The national authority, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports provides multi-annual funding to a research and support centre to provide long-term support to Czech RPOs to ensure that the capacities are built and expert support is provided to address the GEP eligibility criterion. Furthermore, the Centre is tasked with ensuring the commitments of the Czech Republic in relation to the implementation of the ERA Action 5 and contributes to policy coordination between the Czech Republic and EU policy and the policy transfer to the national level.
Website	https://www.soc.cas.cz/en/project/czera-2021-2027

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Gender Equality Plans in Public Sector Research Performing Organizations Reports (CZ)

Name of the measure	Gender Equality Plans in Public Sector Research Performing Organizations Reports (annual reports)
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The aim of the report is to contribute to the fulfilment of the tasks in Gender Equality Strategy for 2021 – 2030 and in National RDI policy 2021+ by mapping the situation in public sector research. The report monitors the existence of Gender Equality Plans and their content based on requirements recommended by the European Commission. This document provides the first analysis of the published GEPs of public sector research organizations in the Czech Republic.
Target group	RDI institutions
Approach/content	Monitoring of Gender Equality Plans of Public Sector Research Performing Organizations. The monitoring focuses on the existence of Gender Equality Plan as well as its content – four mandatory process-based requirements, additional five recommended areas the GEP should contain and other aspects of the GEP.
Results	The analysis shows that the number of institutions with GEP has grown significantly in recent years. The quality of the analysed gender equality plans varies considerably – half of the analysed GEPS fulfil the mandatory requirements and only 44 % of the analysed GEPs contains all of the recommended areas. The GEPs of the HEI are more consistent than the GEPs of public research institutions.
Resources (per year)	It is implemented as part of the tasks of the STRATIN+ project financed by Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	No
Website	https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/#vystupy [in Czech]

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Gender-based Violence Monitoring (CZ)

Name of the measure	Gender-based violence and sexual harassment at universities. The analysis of annual university reports for 2022
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The aim of this report, to be executed on an annual basis, is to analyse the annual reports of higher education institutions for the year 2022 from the point of view of addressing the topics of gender-based violence and sexual harassment and the comparison of the reports with reports from previous years. The monitoring is based on the reports of HEIs which have to report on the issue.
Target group	Higher education institutions, Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
Approach/content	Monitoring of measures reported by HEI to the Ministry Education, Youth and Sport in their annual reports which contain a category of gender-based violence. The monitoring focuses on the types of measures, the number of measures in each report and additional information connected to this issue (for example the process of dealing with issues of gender-based violence and sexual harassment at the institutional level). The monitoring also focuses on the progress of this issue by comparing with the reports from 2017 when it was first introduced.
Results	Reporting in this area moves forward, the information contained in the annual reports tends to be more detailed and specific, the number of measures used to prevent and address cases has also increased. New categories dealing with this issue are added into the reports. Differences still remain in the reporting of individual institutions. 25 out of 26 HEI report at least one measure for gender-based violence and sexual harassment. The most common instruments used by HEIs are Ethics commission, methodological and other documents or the Code of Ethics.
Resources (per year)	It is implemented as part of the duties of the STRATIN+ project financed by Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	No
Website	https://stratin.tc.cas.cz/vystupy/2023/M4/Genderove_podminene_nasili_A5_2023.pdf [in Czech]

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Denmark

Act on Equality between Women and Men (DK)

Name of the measure	Act on Equality between Women and Men
Introduced in	2020
Description of the measure	
Objective	To promote equality between women and men, including equal integration, influence and opportunities in all areas of society and to counteract direct and indirect discrimination based on gender including sexual harassment
Target group	All employers, public authorities and organizations in the public administration and the general economy, public authorities and organizations and all persons providing goods and services available to the public in both the public and private sectors, including public institutions, which are offered outside of private and family life, and the related businesses
Approach/content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prohibition of gender discrimination (directly and indirectly), including sexual harassment • The public sector must promote equality between women and men and take gender equality into account in all planning and administration • Gender balance in decision making: Public committees and commissions that are set up by a minister to prepare the establishment of rules or plans of social importance should have equal representation of women and men • Ministries, state institutions and state-owned companies must report on their work for gender equality every three years before June 1st (state institutions and state-owned companies only have to report if they have more than 50 employees) • The Danish Institute for Human Rights has the task of promoting, assessing, monitoring and supporting equal treatment of women and men (e.g. by providing impartial assistance to victims of discrimination in the hearing of their discrimination complaints, conducting impartial investigations of discrimination, publishing impartial reports and making recommendations on all issues of discrimination)
Results	---
Resources	---
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://recognitionrewards.nl https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2020/1147 (in Danish only)

Source: WP5 desk research

Tripartite agreement on sexual harassment to promote a healthy workplace culture (DK)

Name of the measure	Tripartite agreement on sexual harassment to promote a healthy workplace culture
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	To support a cultural change in the workplace
Target group	Employers and employees
Approach/content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules are clarified so that both employers and employees know their responsibilities and duties, and there will be greater consequences if the workplace does not live up to its obligations • The compensation level in particularly serious cases of sexual harassment is increased by 33 % • Improved legal rights for students and apprentices who are subjected to sexual harassment • Increased focus on sexual harassment in the work environment (including workplace assessments) • Clarify in the rules that employees have a duty to disclose information about sexual harassment at work if they become aware of it and cannot resolve it themselves • Annual reports on the number of decisions and guidelines on sexual harassment and bullying issued by the Danish Working Environment Authority • Establish an alliance with all relevant organizations to ensure a continued focus on sexual harassment
Results	---
Resources (per year)	The government wants to allocate DKK 5 million to the alliance in 2023
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://www.regeringen.dk/nyheder/2022/trepartsaftale-om-seksuel-chikaneskal-fremme-en-sund-kultur-paa-arbejdspladser/ (in Danish only)

Source: WP5 desk research

Finland

Finnish National STEM Strategy and Action Plan 2030 (FI)

Name of the measure	Finnish National STEM Strategy and Action Plan 2030
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	To ensure that there is science and mathematics competence and understanding in society to promote wellbeing and growth that is socially, ecologically and economically sustainable. Strategy objectives include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smooth everyday life, functioning society • STEM competence passes the functions of society • Early childhood education and care and teaching at different levels are of high quality • STEM studies are interesting • Communication about STEM competence and its opportunities will increase
Target group	(early childhood education) teachers, educational institutions
Approach/content	Measures are divided into three categories: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Measures for developing teaching and education 2) Measures for monitoring, surveys and general development 3) Measures for promoting communications and interest
Results	---
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/handle/10024/164953

Source: WP5 desk research

France

Coordination of the network of gender equality officers in RPOs and organization of national events (FR)

Name of the measure	Coordination of the network of gender equality officers in RPOs and organization of national events
Introduced in	2012
Description of the measure	
Objective	The Ministry's role is to coordinate and run the network of gender equality officers in order to support them in the implementation of gender equality plans
Target group	Gender equality officers of all RPOs
Approach/content	The Ministry organizes annual meetings and thematic workshops with the aim of sharing good practices and training. On June 22, 2023, the 8th national day of gender equality officers in Higher Education and Research took place, co-organized by the ministry and the University of Côte d'Azur. The event brought together more than a hundred people. The theme was the integration of gender analysis in research. This is also an opportunity to present ministry news and bring together partner associations. The 9th national day of equality missions will be organized with the University of Clermont Auvergne in June 2024 on the theme of student involvement in the fight against inequalities.
Results	---
Resources (per year)	€ 15.000 for the national day
Innovative elements	Networking between gender equality officers, share of good practices, direct link between gender equality officers and the ministry, sharing of resources and information
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Supporting associations for professional equality and diversity HE & RI (FR)

Name of the measure	Supporting associations for professional equality and diversity HE & RI
Introduced in	2001
Description of the measure	
Objective	The objective is to improve professional equality and diversity across sectors and disciplines in HE & RI
Target group	National associations: Femmes & Sciences, Femmes & Ingénieures, Femmes & mathématiques, Association of women leaders of HE & RI, Becomtech, Prologin
Approach/content	Each year the ministry supports associations and the implementation of their actions via a grant
Results	---
Resources (per year)	€ 30.000
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Supporting RPOs in the elaboration and monitoring of their gender equality plan (FR)

Name of the measure	Supporting RPOs in the elaboration and monitoring of their gender equality plan
Introduced in	2021
Description of the measure	
Objective	In 2019, a law introduced the obligation for all public bodies to elaborate gender equality plans, which enabled higher education and research institutions to reflect on concrete ways of advancing equality between women and men, and to structure the actions already implemented. The objective is to support all RPOs and RFOs in the implementation and evaluation of their GEP.
Target group	RPOs and RFOs (one RFO in France: ANR)
Approach/content	The ministry supports higher education and research institutions in the development, implementation and monitoring of their GEP. It disseminates the methods for monitoring and evaluating plans. The ministry brings together a plan monitoring committee. RPOs are required to submit an annual report on implementation of their GEPs to the Ministry and to an independent body. This body, the High Council for the Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (HCERES) is also responsible for evaluating the GEPs. The ministry is currently in discussion with HCERES to define the evaluation methods
Results	All our institutions have taken part in this process of structuring their GEP
Resources (per year)	None
Innovative elements	Evaluation of GEPs by an external body
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	GEPs allow HEIs to reflect on concrete ways of advancing equality between women and men, and to structure the actions already implemented.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Supporting RPOs in the elaboration of Equality Index to measure gender pay gaps (FR)

Name of the measure	Supporting RPOs in the elaboration of Equality Index to measure gender pay gaps
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The objective of the Equality Index is to measure pay gaps between women and men in RPOs
Target group	RPOs
Approach/content	In application of decree n°2023-1136 of December 5, 2023 relating to the measurement and reduction of pay gaps between women and men in the State civil service, all RPOs under the supervision of the ministry must publish data relating to the equality index. They are subject to 3 indicators: 1) Overall pay gap between women and men, for civil servants, calculated from the average pay of women compared to that of men, for equivalent bodies, grades and levels ; 2) Overall pay gap between women and men, for contract agents, calculated from the average pay of women compared to that of men, in equivalent hierarchical category ; 3) Number of public officials of the under-represented sex among the 10 % public officials having received the highest remuneration.
Results	---
Resources (per year)	None
Innovative elements	Before 2023 the equality index did not apply to public establishments; transparency on pay gaps between men and women in RPOs; it allows comparison
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	Transparency on pay gaps between men and women in RPOs; it allows comparison
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Irène Joliot-Curie Prize (FR)

Name of the measure	Irène Joliot-Curie Prize
Introduced in	2001
Description of the measure	
Objective	This prize is one of the measures taken to fight against the Mathilda effect and to give more visibility to women scientists and their work, in order to create new models
Target group	Women scientists
Approach/content	In 2023, the ministry, in partnership with the Academy of Sciences, rewarded 6 women scientists in 4 categories: the woman scientist of the year, 3 young women scientists, the "woman, research and business" and the special prize of the "commitment". This prize rewarded a woman particularly involved in guiding and raising awareness on gender stereotypes in STEM careers.
Results	Since the creation of this prize, 70 women have been rewarded. The majority of "Women scientists" have joined Academies. The "young woman scientist" award helps launch researchers' careers.
Resources (per year)	€ 162.000
Innovative elements	Prize for women scientists
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	Gives visibility to women scientists and gives new representations to future generations
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Rixain Decrees (FR)

Name of the measure	Rixain Decrees
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The Rixain Decrees aim at improving our knowledge of inequalities of opportunity between women and men in higher education and research through the publication of indicators
Target group	Higher school preparatory classes & RPOs
Approach/content	In application of the law of December 24, 2021, aimed at accelerating professional and economic equality between women and men, the ministry elaborated 3 implementing decrees. These 3 decrees specify the indicators relating to equal opportunities and the means implemented to combat inequalities, which must be published by RPOs annually on their website.
Results	These indicators will be published in December 2024
Resources (per year)	None
Innovative elements	Publication on websites each year
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	It provides information and transparency on gender inequalities in HE&RI organizations, and allows to follow evolution of gender inequalities
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Tech for all (Tech pour Toutes) (FR)

Name of the measure	Tech for all (Tech pour Toutes)
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The objective of the “Tech pour Toutes” programme is to bring and support 10,000 girls and women in digital sectors
Target group	15-25 years old girls and women
Approach/content	The Inria foundation is mandated to implement the Tech for All programme in order to combat the underrepresentation of women in the digital sector. The program aims to support 10,000 girls from the end of high school to professional integration in partnership with stakeholders in this ecosystem (associations, schools, businesses)
Results	---
Resources (per year)	Under discussion
Innovative elements	The global and coordinated approach with all stakeholders in the ecosystem and different ministries involved (ministry of national education, ministry of higher education and research, and the ministry of equality)
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	Growing need for girls in these sectors; global and coordinated approach
Website	https://www.techpourtoutes.io/ (in French only)

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Trainings on professional equality for RPOs' staff (FR)

Name of the measure	Trainings on professional equality for RPOs' staff
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	A cycle of national webinars was put in place to train all RPOs' staff on issues of professional equality, parenthood and work-life balance, recruitment, fight against violence based on gender identity & sexual orientation.
Target group	RPOs' staff (gender equality offices, human resources, legal affairs, services management)
Approach/content	4 webinars of 1h30 each facilitated by independent experts.
Results	200 participants at each seminar, average rating of 4.5/5 satisfaction by participants
Resources (per year)	€ 6.000
Innovative elements	First time that the ministry offers professional equality training through webinars
Evaluation	Yes, but not public yet
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. Reaches a wide audience, easy organization
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

GBV Trainings (FR)

Name of the measure	GBV Trainings
Introduced in	2021
Description of the measure	
Objective	Massive and systematic training is the first main objective of the national GBV policy in higher education and research. Training and awareness-raising sessions targeting all the higher education and research community are essential to change attitudes and practices. Those involved in dealing with situations of sexist and sexual violence, presidents and directors of institutions as well as those involved in doctoral training are among the audiences defined as priority in terms of access to GBV training.
Target group	All RPOs; academic and non-academic staff
Approach/content	The Ministry financially supports two associations that provide onsite one day trainings for 1) members within listening and reporting units in RPOs, and 2) members in charge of disciplinary proceedings. In addition, the GBV Office within the General Inspectorate of Education, Sport and Research provides online trainings on investigative procedures: one for investigators and a second one targeting RPOs' top management.
Results	2023: 20 training sessions from the two associations - 550 staff members trained. The General Inspectorate organized 4 training sessions in 2023, 1000 staff members trained.
Resources (per year)	€ 1,100.000 (2023)
Innovative elements	The innovative element is the goal to professionalize both members of reporting units and GBV cases investigators.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

National communication campaign on GBV (FR)

Name of the measure	National communication campaign on GBV
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	In October 2022, a national communication campaign on the notion of sexual consent was launched. In December 2023, the campaign was shared again on social media and newspapers. The objective is to build a common culture around consent and the fight against GBV in higher education and research. The campaign seeks to challenge, question and raise awareness in the community about the notion of consent. Link to the campaign: https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/consentement
Target group	All RPOs; students, academic and non-academic staff
Approach/content	The campaign was co-elaborated with the “Sexe & Consentement” association, drawing on its field experience and the numerous training and awareness actions carried out among the higher education and research community since several years. The campaign comes in two formats: 1) a dematerialized communication kit composed of a set of posters and a social media kit; 2) a special communication on social media, in partnership with Konbini (online newspaper) and the Sexe et Consentement association, made up of two videos (advice and testimonials) and an Instagram quiz. In December 2023, it was shared again on social media and print newspapers.
Results	2022: 3.5 million views on social media 6 months after its launch
Resources (per year)	€ 618.000 (2021-2023)
Innovative elements	The innovative element is to focus on the notion of sexual consent.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	A national campaign on the topic of sexual consent is both a means to raise awareness on GBV and consent, but also to make the reporting unit and local resources known to student and staff community
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

National listening, support and reporting system for students (FR)

Name of the measure	National listening, support and reporting system for students
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	The Ministry has set up a national listening, support and reporting system for students who experience situations of discomfort, violence or discrimination. A professional, free and confidential helpline has been set up (0 800 737 800) and is operated by a feminist association specialized on GBV (En Avant Toutes). Professionals (psychologists, social workers) ensure listening and reorientation towards appropriate resources.
Target group	Students from both public and private RPOs
Approach/content	This measure provides support for students who experience discrimination, violence or any issue that may have an impact on their physical and psychological well-being. The helpline is complementary to those implemented at the local level by higher education and research institutions.
Results	[Partially available] Number of calls (January and February): 389 / GBV cases processed: 11
Resources (per year)	€ 350.000 (2023)
Innovative elements	National helpline for students with professionals trained on GBV and LGBTQ+ experiences.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	This national helpline run by a recognized feminist association is an additional resource for students who may not find adequate resources locally or who may not feel safe to go their local listening and reporting unit. It is also an additional tool to collect data on GBV.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Online learning module on GBV for students (FR)

Name of the measure	Online learning module for students
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	IMT Atlantique (public engineering school) elaborated an online learning module on GBV for students (3h-4h), open to any higher education and research institution. The Ministry has funded the module. English subtitles are available.
Target group	All RPOs; students
Approach/content	The training module is structured around 7 topics: disciplinary procedure, legal framework, notion of consent, GBV among students, victims and bystanders, sociology of GBV, and the role of student associations.
Results	Around 70 RPOs have registered to use and disseminate the module within their own student community.
Resources (per year)	€ 1,100.000 (2023)
Innovative elements	The online learning module is available and free for any higher education and research institution.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	This 4h online learning module for students is an interesting first step to raise awareness around GBV among students, and also to make the local reporting units and resources known to them.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Promoting student and staff initiatives (FR)

Name of the measure	Promoting student and staff initiatives
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	Extending the 2022 funding campaign, the ministry launched a new edition of the campaign “Promoting the commitment of students and staff in the fight against gender-based and sexual violence” in 2023. The objective of these campaigns is to financially support local initiatives, which provide a new perspective, innovative ideas and concrete actions to tackle GBV within RPOs.
Target group	All RPOs & RFOs; students, academic and non-academic staff
Approach/content	The student community and staff of higher education and research institutions develop a large number of initiatives (prevention and training actions, communication campaigns, etc.) addressing gender-based violence. The ministry wished to support these field initiatives, which are essential to bring about cultural and institutional change.
Results	2022: 35 projects were funded, total of € 350.000. 2023: 51 projects were funded, total of € 520.000
Resources (per year)	2022: € 350.000, 2023: € 520.000
Innovative elements	The innovative element is the focus on student initiatives.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	Yes and no: the measure is important to fund local initiatives; however, the calls for project entail an important administrative workload at the Ministry level.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Reinforcement of reporting units in RPOs by increasing cooperation between stakeholders (FR)

Name of the measure	Reinforcement of reporting units in RPOs by increasing cooperation between stakeholders: 37 new coordination positions focused on GBV and student well-being in regional administrative authorities
Introduced in	2023-2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	37 project officers positions newly created in the 18 French academic regions in order to support RPOs on the implementation of their preventive measures against GBV; the strengthening of their reporting units and their investigative procedures.
Target group	All RPOs; students, academic and non-academic staff
Approach/content	The Ministry for Higher Education and Research has reinforced its national policy to end GBV by moving to a new scale of cooperation between stakeholders, reinforcing the role of its decentralized administrative authorities with coordination positions focused on GBV-related issues.
Results	---
Resources (per year)	€ 1,300.000 (2023)
Innovative elements	The innovative element is the reinforced role that decentralized administrative authorities (regions) will now play in implementing the GBV national policy and in supporting case managers and investigators within RPOs.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	For countries that have a similar administrative system than France, this measure provides a good example of how to ensure the concrete implementation of a national policy through dedicated full time positions at the level of decentralized administrative authorities.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Supporting national associations addressing GBV and LGBTQIA+ rights (FR)

Name of the measure	Supporting national associations
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	In November 2023, the Minister wished to reinforce its support for national associations specialized in the fight against GBV and violence based on sexual orientation & gender identity. The goal is to strengthen their prevention initiatives as well as their services provided to victims.
Target group	National associations addressing GBV and LGBTQIA+ rights
Approach/content	2 years partnerships in order to develop ambitious, long-term projects.
Results	9 national associations have partnered with the Ministry (7 of them were already receiving funds since 2021). 3 associations dedicated to LGBTQIA+ rights partnered for the first time with the Ministry.
Resources (per year)	2023: total budget = € 1,300.000 for 2 years
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. This measure is essential as it valorises the active role of national associations on the ground and their specific expertise
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Working group on trans rights (FR)

Name of the measure	Working group on trans rights
Introduced in	2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	A working group has been set up in February 2024 to address both violence based on gender identity and the access to rights and services within RPOs for trans and non-binary staff and students. The objective of the working group is to better understand the issues faced by trans and non-binary students and staff and to make recommendations to higher education and research institutions.
Target group	All RPOs; academic and non-academic staff
Approach/content	The working group is composed of representatives from RPOs, gender equality officers, specializes associations (trans organizations), researchers in queer & sociology studies, LGBTQI+ Research Chair, and policy officers from the Ministry who work on LGBT+ rights issues. The work programme is structured around 4 main topics: 1) producing & promoting research and data on experiences of trans staff and students, 2) elaborating structural change measures, 3) implementing training and resources, 4) addressing GBV
Results	---
Resources (per year)	None as for now
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Germany

(HRK) Initiative – Diversity at German universities (DE)

Name of the measure	HRK-Initiative “Vielfalt an deutschen Hochschulen“ - German Rectors' Conference (HRK) Initiative – Diversity at German universities
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	The aim of the initiative is to support institutions of higher education to further develop holistic diversity concepts.
Target group	Institutions of higher education
Approach/content	First-time initiative for Institutions of higher education to hand in diversity concepts --> funding for these projects/campaigns; final conference in April 2024 will serve to take stock and define future steps required for further developing diversity approaches. joint initiative by BMBF and HRK (German University Rectors Conference)
Results	33 projects funded; exchange between projects; final conference end of April 2024
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The measure aims at enabling practical approaches to diversity at German universities, as well as an exchange between projects. This approach allows accounting for the specific situation at different universities while at the same time fostering an exchange on lessons learned and best practices.
Website	https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/shareddocs/faq/vielfalt-an-hochschulen.html https://www.hrk.de/themen/hochschulsystem/diversitaet/ (both in German only)

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Programme for Women Professors of the German Federal Government and the Länder (DE)

Name of the measure	Professorinnenprogramm des Bundes und der Länder (Programme for Women Professors of the German Federal Government and the Länder)
Introduced in	2008 (currently, Phase IV since 2023)
Description of the measure	
Objective	Germany's biggest initiative of the Federal Government and the Länder to improve gender equality in science and research. It increases the number of female professors while supporting the implementation of structural gender equality measures. Goal: Contribute to achieving gender parity in science by 2030.
Target group	Institutions of higher education
Approach/content	The programme works on two levels: It increases the number of women professors in Institutions of higher education and it strengthens equal opportunities structures through specific measures. Institutions of higher education wanting to participate in the programme develop gender equality strategies which are evaluated by an independent, high-profile expert panel. In a second step, Institutions of higher education whose strategy received a positive evaluation are able to apply for up to three lots of kick-off funding to finance first-time appointments of women to W2 and W3 professorships with a maximum five-year tenure. Appointments to a professorship can be made in anticipation of a future vacancy or a position yet to be created (anticipatory professorship) or to an existing position (regular professorship). When requesting funding for a regular professorship, the universities agree to use funds freed up by the programme together with other financial resources to introduce additional gender equality measures.
Results	A total of 852 funded professorships in the first three program phases (as of March 31, 2024); contribution to increasing the proportion of female professors at German universities; contribution to closing the gap between the representation of women and men in science; the program was strengthened in terms of content in a fourth phase and will run until 2030
Resources (per year)	For the current phase (2023-2030) a total of € 320,000.000 (funding by equal share by the Federal Government and the Länder)
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	Yes, see: Microsoft Word - 220315_3470_Eval_PP III_Abschlussbericht.docx (gwk-bonn.de) (in German only)
Recommendation	Yes. The Programme for Women Professors is a best practice example of how

as good practice	positive incentives can lead to organisations working more intensively and more effectively on making equal opportunities a reality for ALL scientists.
Website	https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/de/forschung/gleichstellung-und-vielfalt-im-wissenschaftssystem/frauen-im-wissenschaftssystem/frauen-im-wissenschaftssystem_node.html (in German only)

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Promotion of structures for the systematic consideration of gender-related aspects in research questions (DE)

Name of the measure	Förderung von Strukturen zur systematischen Berücksichtigung von geschlechtsbezogenen Aspekten in Forschungsfragen (Geschlechteraspekte im Blick) - Promotion of structures for the systematic consideration of gender-related aspects in research questions (Gender aspects in focus)
Introduced in	2021
Description of the measure	
Objective	Promotion of structures for the systematic consideration of gender-related aspects in research questions: improving the life of all human beings, regardless of their sex/gender, age or other aspects of diversity; strengthening Germany's excellence and international competitiveness in research, development and innovation; gaining scientific knowledge about the causes and mechanisms that hinder equality.
Target group	Institutions of higher education, research organisations and SMEs doing research
Approach/content	Funding for innovative structural projects with model character that systematically and permanently integrate gender aspects into the research process.
Results	55 project applications in concept phase, 36 of them being funded in the implementation phase (starting in spring 2024); first networking meeting for all projects in the implementation phase foreseen for spring/summer 2024.
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The interdisciplinary approach allows addressing aspects of gender studies in an orchestrated way. The two-step process of concept and implementation phase dedicates funding to the most convincing projects; but at the same time, the concept phase already sparks impulses and new networks within the gender studies research community.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Ireland

Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Higher Education Institutions, Implementation Plan, 2022-2024 (IE)

Name of the measure	The 'Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Higher Education Institutions, Implementation Plan, 2022-2024' (ESVH Implementation Plan)
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	The ESVH Implementation Plan sets out 19 actions that respond directly to the recommendations that emerged from national surveys conducted by the Higher Education Authority (HEA) in 2022.
Target group	The Irish higher education sector (including Higher Education Institutions, the Higher Education Authority and representative bodies)
Approach/content	The ESVH Implementation Plan sets out 19 actions that represent a comprehensive and ambitious response to the data that emerged from national staff and student surveys. Actions in the Implementation Plan include (summarised here): Awareness-raising, education and training for staff and students, integrate survey findings into initiatives, a conference to explore the feasibility of a panel of investigators, pilot initiatives with high risk and hard-to-reach groups, mapping of training initiatives and reporting mechanisms, explore the feasibility of standardised training, conduct further research, review the national framework outcomes
Results	A national conference on ending sexual violence and harassment (December 2022), social media campaigns on consent (11 million views), a feasibility study to explore the establishment of a trauma-informed investigation shared service for the Higher Education sector was completed.
Resources (per year)	This work draws on the wider resources allocated to the implementation of the national policy framework.
Innovative elements	The promotion of sectoral approaches, collaboration and stakeholder engagement.
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2021/04/HEA_ESVH_Implementation_Plan_FINAL.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions (IE)

Name of the measure	The national policy framework, entitled 'Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions'.
Introduced in	2019
Description of the measure	
Objective	The framework sets out a strategy to achieve its vision of a safe, respectful and supportive campus culture for all in which institutions fulfil their duty of care towards staff and students
Target group	Irish higher education institutions (all staff and students)
Approach/content	The framework sets out principles for action and advocates for a whole-of-system approach. It details 15 holistic outcomes across four core pillars, which higher education institutions (HEIs) are expected to implement. Outcomes in the framework include (summarised here): Assigning senior level responsibility, establishment of a cross-institutional working group, engaging in external specialist partnerships, collation and reporting of data on incidences of SVH to the HEA, establishment of accessible, survivor-centred disclosure and reporting mechanisms and raising awareness of these, the development of institutional policies with regular progress reports to Governing Authorities, targeted interventions including awareness-raising, skills-building and training, trauma-informed support services, monitoring effectiveness
Results	A reporting system is in place whereby institutions report on progress against the framework to the Higher Education Authority on an annual basis, senior level responsibility for addressing sexual violence and harassment assigned in all core-funded institutions, most institutions have established a cross-institutional working group that meets on a regular basis, most institutions have established partnerships with external specialist agencies to support this work, national surveys on experiences of sexual violence and harassment in higher education institutions have been completed with staff and students (leading to the ESVH Implementation Plan 2022-2024), an online anonymous reporting system is in place in most core-funded institutions, a system for HEIs to report aggregated data on formal complaints and investigations related to SVH to the Higher Education Authority has been established, several institutions have developed relevant dedicated policies and procedures, an active ESVH Practitioner Network has been established and meets on a regular basis, most institutions have integrated an information session on sexual violence and consent in first year undergraduate orientation sessions, increasing numbers of staff and students participating in education and training initiatives related to address sexual violence, such as bystander and disclosure training, a small number of strategic pilot initiatives in institutions have been provided with financial support.
Resources (per year)	€241,000.00 in 2023 for the implementation of the Framework. Since 2023, €1,500,000.00 per annum has been allocated to support the appointment of dedicated Sexual Violence and Harassment Prevention and Response Managers in Irish higher education institutions.

Innovative elements	Whole of system approach
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned.
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The national policy framework has been instrumental in driving a consistent and holistic approach across the sector and in providing a strong mandate for action and resourcing, in addition to facilitating stakeholder engagement an improved data collection.
Website	https://assets.gov.ie/24925/57c394e5439149d087ab589d0ff39c92.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Race Equality in the Irish Higher Education Sector – survey and report (IE)

Name of the measure	Race Equality in the Irish Higher Education Sector – survey and report
Introduced in	2020
Description of the measure	
Objective	The HEA Centre of Excellence for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion ran the first National Race Equality Survey of Irish higher education institutions. The aim of the survey was to capture the lived experience of HEI staff in relation to race equality.
Target group	Higher education institution staff in Ireland
Approach/content	All staff working in HEIs in the Republic of Ireland, regardless of ethnic background or nationality, were invited to participate in the first National Race Equality Survey. 3,323 staff in Irish HEIs responded to the survey. As the aim of the survey was to capture the lived experience of HEI staff in relation to race equality, a number of open questions were used in the survey, leading to 6,536 individual open text responses to the survey. The survey results were collated in a report to provide an overall picture of race equality across the Irish higher education sector and to help to identify areas for improvement, as well as ways to make those improvements. Thirty-two recommendations were made in the report.
Results	Results of the first National Race Equality Survey of all HEIs were published in the report, Race Equality in the higher education sector in October 2021.
Resources (per year)	This work draws on the wider resources allocated to the implementation of the national policy framework for EDI.
Innovative elements	Survey was innovative as first survey on race equality in Irish HEIs.
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2021/10/HEA-Race-Equality-in-the-Higher-Education-Sector-Analysis-commissioned-by-the-Higher-Education-Authority-1.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Race Equality Implementation Plan 2022-2024 (IE)

Name of the measure	Race Equality Implementation Plan 2022-2024
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	In September 2022, the HEA launched the Race Equality Implementation Plan 2022-2024, containing nine actions which relate to the recommendations of the Race Equality Report. To advance race equality across the Irish higher education sector and to aid in the implementation of the 32 recommendations from the Race Equality Report, 2021.
Target group	Higher Education Institutions in Ireland
Approach/content	In March 2022, the HEA prepared a discussion paper proposing a number of actions to implement the recommendations in the report. The discussion paper was issued for feedback to the Athena SWAN Ireland Intersectionality Working Group, higher education institutions and the HEA National Committee for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion. This feedback was incorporated into an Implementation Plan. In September 2022, the HEA launched the Race Equality Implementation Plan 2022-2024.
Results	Actions contained in the Implementation Plan have begun to be implemented by the HEA and higher education institutions. While progress has been made, implementation of all actions is not yet complete.
Resources (per year)	This work draws on the wider resources allocated to the implementation of the national policy framework for EDI.
Innovative elements	Whole of system approach. Includes specific actions for HEIs.
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2022/03/HEA-Race-Equality-Implementation-Plan-2022-2024.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Anti-Racism Principles for Irish Higher Education Institutions (IE)

Name of the measure	Anti-Racism Principles for Irish Higher Education Institutions
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	The HEA developed the Anti-Racism Principles which aim to harness the power that Irish Higher Education Institutions have as leaders of positive change in society to challenge racism and race inequality. The aim of the principles is to recognise the definition of racism as delineated by the National Anti-Racism Committee and contain principles which will ensure institution leaders take responsibility, accountability and ownership of race equality issues within their institution. Institutions were requested to sign up to the principles, which ensure active acknowledgement that race inequality exists in the Irish HE sector, acknowledging that assertive action is needed by HEIs to keep pace with wider demographics to catch up with global counterparts. The principles also recognise the power that the HEIs have to influence Irish society more broadly.
Target group	Higher education institution staff in Ireland
Approach/content	Following the launch of the Implementation Plan in 2022, which included the development of a national race equality charter. In line with the terminology used in broader government policy in relation to tackling racism and race inequality it was decided to frame this document as a set of “Anti-Racism Principles for Irish HEIs”, rather than as a Charter/Statement on Race Equality. The principles address the recommendations in the Race Equality Report, which call on HEI leadership to actively embed a culture of race equality within HEIs. A draft version of these principles was developed by the HEA Centre of Excellence for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion in collaboration with the Athena Swan Ireland Intersectionality Working Group and external stakeholders. The Anti-Racism Principles were published in March 2023.
Results	By the start of 2024, all publicly funded Irish higher education institutions had signed and endorsed the principles.
Resources (per year)	This work draws on the wider resources allocated to the implementation of the national policy framework for EDI.
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. Signing up to the principles is a way for HEIs to make a visible commitment and first step towards advancing race equality and build support for further work.
Website	https://hea.ie/assets/uploads/2022/03/Anti-Racism-Principles-for-Irish-Higher-Education-Institutions.pdf

Source: WP5 survey 2024

2nd HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions (IE)

Name of the measure	2 nd HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions
Introduced in	2022
Description of the measure	
Objective	In 2016, the (first) HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions, produced a set of recommendations to ensure the achievement of gender equality in Irish higher education (HE). The 2017 Gender Action Plan endorsed the first review recommendations and developed some additional actions to advance gender equality across the sector. In line with recommended progress reviews, the HEA undertook a Second National Review of Gender Equality in Irish HEIs in 2022.
Target group	All staff in the higher education sector in Ireland. This includes academic, research and professional, managerial and support staff (PMSS).
Approach/content	The Expert Group, comprised of 6 national and international gender equality experts, prepared an online consultation of Higher Education staff in relation to gender equality in HEIs (in line with the survey which was ran in 2015 for the 1 st review). The consultation was open from 30 th March until 29 th April 2022 and was circulated to all staff in HEIs in Ireland. There was a total of 2,025 full responses. Along with the online consultation, written submissions were also requested and 17 were received. The Expert Group also met with several stakeholder groups to discuss progress made towards advancing gender equality since the first review in 2016.
Results	The overarching recommendations from the Review were: National Requirements: At a minimum all Irish higher education institutions should: have an institutional Gender Equality Action Plan that is published on the HEI website, signed by the President, actively communicated and progress monitored within the institution; demonstrate a commitment to provide sufficient resources and expertise in gender equality, particularly in relation to the implementation of its institutional Gender Equality Action Plan; have a Vice-President (or equivalent) with responsibility for EDI who is a member of the HEI Executive/Management Team; collect and analyse sex/gender-disaggregated data on staff to inform the institutional strategy for advancement of gender equality; and provide training towards sustaining the advancement of gender equality for all staff. A number of recommendations were also made in the areas of Leadership, Organisational Culture, Teaching and Learning, Research and Quality Assurance, Intersectionality, Career Development, Precarity, Data Capture, Analysis and Reporting. While some significant progress has been made, it was clear that many of the recommendations made in the 2016 review and in the 2018 Gender Action Plan remained valid. The Expert Group recommended that national progress be subject to periodic review every 5 years.
Resources (per year)	This work draws on the wider resources allocated to the implementation of the national policy framework. From 2020-2023, under the Gender Equality Enhancement Fund, the HEA awarded a total of € 250.000 per annum to groups of HEIs for collaborative projects to advance gender equality, including

	those that respond to the recommendations of the second review.
Innovative elements	Whole of system approach. A set of national requirements were recommended by the Expert Group which sets out a baseline for HEIs. Recommendations were made relating to precarity and centralising intersectionality (rather than just accommodating intersectionality).
Evaluation	Not yet, but an evaluation is planned. In 2024 HEIs have submitted their first reports relating to the implementation of the recommendations of the second review. The Expert Group recommends that national progress be subject to periodic review every 5 years.
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. The review was an opportunity to add to the evidence base for gender equality work and policy, seek input from national and international experts and stakeholders. The review was an opportunity to reflect on progress made since the 1 st review in 2016 and to assess and set out recommendations to address new challenges for the sector arising since the 1 st review.
Website	https://hea.ie/policy/gender/hea-national-review-of-gender-equality-in-irish-higher-education-institutions/

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Israel

Multiyear Plan for Gender Fairness in Academia (IL)

Name of the measure	Multiyear Plan for Gender Fairness in Academia
Introduced in	2018
Description of the measure	
Objective	The promotion of women in academia with a focus on senior faculty members and raising awareness of gender equality at higher education institutions
Target group	Women in academia
Approach/content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scholarship for women post-doctoral students will be increased significantly from up to \$ 50.000 for two years to \$ 80.000 for two years • Women post-doctoral students in high-tech fields will receive scholarships of 150.000 NIS (for three years) and women master's students in high-tech fields will receive scholarships of 80.000 NIS (for two years). A total of 1,000.000 NIS annually will be given as prizes of excellence to institutions that excel in gender fairness • For the first time, academic institutions will be asked to publish an annual gender report on their website, in accordance with the regulations of the European Union • For the first time, the PBC is allocating a special budget to the activity of president advisors on gender fairness at institutions of higher learning (total budget: up to 120.000 NIS per institution) • Hiring and promotion of women among academic staff members in general, particularly in fields in which women are underrepresented
Results	---
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	An output-based index was published for the promotion of gender fairness at institutions that are budgeted by the PBC for the years 2020-2025 ("Equator Index"). The purpose of the index is to incentivize institutions to examine the challenges they face in this context and to take measures to increase women's representation.
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://che.org.il/en/the-new-multiannual-program/multi-annual-plan-for-gender-fairness-in-academia/ ; https://che.org.il/en/באקדמיה-נישים/#the-gender-fairness-plan-to-increase-the-representation-of-women-among-academic-staff-members

Source: WP5 desk research

Lithuania

Support for activities aimed at implementing the priorities of the European Research Area for institutional change (LT)

Name of the measure	Support for activities aimed at implementing the priorities of the European Research Area (ERA) for institutional change
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	Implementing ERA actions 3,4,5,9,11,12,13 and 14
Target group	Research and study institutions included in the register of the Open Information, Counseling and Guidance System
Approach/content	Research organisations can apply for up to € 60.000 funding to implement ERA actions
Results	---
Resources (per year)	€ 2,000.000 RRF are allocated for this initiative
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://2021.esinvesticijos.lt/kvietimai/parama-veikloms-skirtoms-europos-moksliniu-tyrimu-erdves-prioritetams-igyvendinti-siekiant-instituciniu-pokyciu

Source: WP5 desk research

The Netherlands

Recognition & Rewards (NL)

Name of the measure	Recognition & Rewards
Introduced in	2019
Description of the measure	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • diversifying and vitalising career paths • achieving balance between individuals and the collective • stimulating open science • focusing on the quality of work instead of quantitative results (such as number of publications) • stimulating academic leadership • achieving a healthy and open academic culture
Target group	Academic institutions, academics and academic leaders
Approach/content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translating the strategy into a Strategic Personnel Plan (SPP) in which departments and other organisational units describe the talents they need in order to realise their vision (Diversification is key) • Recognition & Rewards will determine how the contribution to the collective will be rewarded and how it fits into career policy • Taking differences between disciplines into account, sharing good practices, engaging in national coordination, actively involving the appointment advisory committees in these changes (e.g. by organising training courses) • Focusing on good leadership at all job levels • Visualising the progress of culture change through the Recognition & Rewards culture barometer questionnaire
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutions set up a Recognition & Rewards committee • Universities and institutes wrote vision documents • Numerous experiments have been launched to put the principles of Recognition & Rewards into practice • New career paths have been created and assessment criteria have been changed (e.g. Strategy Evaluation Protocol 2021-2027 was designed in line with the principles of Recognition & Rewards)
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	Shaping a new system of recognition and rewards and a new way of assessing research
Evaluation	Yes, accompanied by annual appraisal interviews
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://recognitionrewards.nl/

Source: WP5 desk research

Norway

Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (KIF Committee) 2022–2025 (NO)

Name of the measure	Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (KIF Committee) 2022–2025
Introduced in	The first committee was appointed in 2004 (“Committee for Mainstreaming – Women in Science”)
Description of the measure	
Objective	The goal is to support and give recommendations regarding measures that promote the integration of gender balance and diversity activities at universities, university colleges and research institutes and thus promote gender equality and diversity. The committee shall seek to raise the overall level of awareness of issues related to diversity, inclusion and harassment at higher education and research institutions.
Target group	Actors and institutions in the higher education sector and research institute sector, ministries, the Norwegian Directorate of Higher Education and Skills, the Research Council of Norway
Approach/content	It receives its mandate from the Ministry of Education and Research and is appointed for four years. The committee shall see the situation in Norway in an international context and be a driving force in international efforts to promote gender balance and diversity. Tasks include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving advice about gender balance and diversity • Visiting research institutions • Organising seminars, communication activities and dissemination of research • Developing guidelines and tools • Giving policy advice to national authorities • Giving advice on an international level
Results	---
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	---
Evaluation	---
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://kifinfo.no/en/content/mandate-committee-gender-balance-and-diversity-research-kif

Source: WP5 desk research

Poland

Systemic institutional and structural change (through GEPs) (PL)

Name of the measure	Measure focused on the objective to achieve systemic institutional and structural change, i.e. supporting the uptake of (inclusive) gender equality plans
Introduced in	2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	The primary aim of the study is to diagnose the level of implementation of Gender Equality Plans in institutions that make up the higher education and science system in Poland as well as the impact of the Plans on the changes taking place at the institutions.
Target group	Polish research and higher education institutions that have developed Gender Equality Plans.
Approach/content	The goal will be achieved by analysing the contents of the GEPs identified on the institutions' websites as well as analysis of the survey to be filled in by the institutional gender equality officers who are responsible for implementing the Plans. The result of the study will be an analytical report submitted to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. The survey and GEPs detailed analysis are also meant to provide input into the research project to be carried out by the National Information Processing Institute in the future. During the course of the GEPs monitoring process both quantitative and quantitative methods will be used, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the subject of the study. The process is divided into the following stages: 1) Identification of GEPs via web scraping; 2) GEPs contents analysis (compliance with Horizon Europe requirements and with recommended areas for GEPs); 3) on-line survey among the research and higher education institutions in Poland; 4) preparation of analytical reports for the Ministry.
Results	Results are not yet available. The draft survey has been prepared, it is currently being consulted between the Ministry of Science and Higher Education and the National Information Processing Institute.
Resources (per year)	€ 100.000
Innovative elements	Apart from the fact that the study focuses on GEPs content analysis, the GEP monitoring study takes to a very large degree the institutional GE officers' perspective into account. The proposed survey questions are meant to explore the GE officers' perception of both his/her work on GEP implementation (cooperation inside the institution, question of sufficient resources, self-assessment of one's knowledge, capacities, skills) and his/her psychological well-being as the person implementing the GEP.

Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. This is a large-scale innovative study conducted in the widening country where gender equality measures had not been introduced prior to the Horizon Europe requirements.
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Portugal

RESTART (PT)

Name of the measure	RESTART
Introduced in	2023
Description of the measure	
Objective	This mechanism allows for a competitive return to research activities on an equal standing, supporting research on a basis of innovative and original ideas
Target group	Researchers, women, men, who have recently benefitted from a parental leave, including adoption
Approach/content	RESTART promotes the competitive funding to individual projects in all scientific domains, when developed by researchers, women, men, who have recently benefitted from a parental leave, including adoption. The programme also includes specific eligibility conditions, as in case of shared parental leaves, privileging care and the share of family responsibilities and the duration of the leave, this mechanism allows for a competitive return to research activities on an equal standing, supporting research on a basis of innovative and original ideas; Special programme providing fund in all scientific areas
Results	2nd edition in 2024
Resources (per year)	1st edition: € 50.000 of funding per project. For this call, a total budget of € 1,600.000 is predicted. https://www.fct.pt/en/concursos/programa-restart-2-edicao € 50.000 2nd edition; euros of funding per project. For this call, a total budget of € 1,250.000 is predicted.
Innovative elements	Specific eligibility conditions, allowing for women and men on a parental break to have a return period to adapt, while benefiting from competitive funding, privileging care and share of family responsibilities
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	---
Website	https://www.fct.pt/en/concursos/programa-restart-1

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Spain

Study on intersectionality (ES)

Name of the measure	Study on intersectionality
Introduced in	2025
Description of the measure	
Objective	To publish a study on how to collect data and design policies in the R&I from an intersectional perspective
Target group	Decision-makers at R&I institutions and GE structures in R&I
Approach/content	To be decided
Results	Not yet
Resources (per year)	To be confirmed
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Not yet
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

Study on GBV protocols at Spanish universities (ES)

Name of the measure	Study on GBV protocols at Spanish universities
Introduced in	2024
Description of the measure	
Objective	To publish a study on the status and functioning of GBV protocols at Spanish universities, with a special focus on the role and perspective of GE structures
Target group	Decision-makers and GE structures at public and private universities
Approach/content	Descriptive statistics plus interviews with gender equality experts
Results	To be published
Resources (per year)	---
Innovative elements	None
Evaluation	No
Recommendation as good practice	Yes. A joint analysis of the status of the protocols may help improve the prevention of GBV in HEIs
Website	---

Source: WP5 survey 2024

